

Validation of the typology and classification system in Bulgaria for assessment the ecological status of surface water bodies of categories “river”, “lake” and “transitional waters”

Final Report

Annex 5

Methods for the analysis of BQEs, reference conditions and the ecological status classification system in the target types of surface waters

BENTHIC INVERTEBRATES

Authors:

Georg WOLFRAM

Emilia VARADINOVA

Monika GROSSSCHARTNER

Rabia SOUFI

Wolfram STOCKINGER

In partnership with

umweltbundesamt^U Deltares

World Bank Contract reference: 7195735

THE WORLD BANK

Content

ABBREVIATIONS	4
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	4
1 INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES ACCORDING TO THE TOR	5
2 AVAILABLE DATA ON MACROINVERTEBRATES AND PRESSURES	6
2.1 MONITORING SITES	6
2.2 BIOLOGICAL DATA.....	7
2.3 BIOLOGICAL METRICS.....	8
2.4 PHYSICAL-CHEMICAL DATA.....	9
2.5 HYDROMORPHOLOGICAL PRESSURES.....	10
2.6 CORINE LANDCOVER	10
3 RIVERS	11
3.1 DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSES OF THE BIOLOGICAL COMMUNITY.....	11
3.2 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN BIOLOGICAL INDICES.....	12
3.3 SIGNIFICANT IMPACT FACTORS.....	13
3.3.1 <i>PHYSICAL-CHEMICAL PARAMETERS</i>	14
3.3.2 <i>HYDROMORPHOLOGICAL PRESSURES</i>	14
3.3.3 <i>CORINE LANDCOVER (CLC)</i>	15
3.4 PRESSURE – RESPONSE RELATIONSHIP	16
3.4.1 <i>PRESSURE INDEX CALCULATION</i>	16
3.4.2 <i>RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PRESSURE INDEX AND BIOTIC INDEX BI</i>	16
3.5 REFERENCE CONDITIONS AND CLASS BOUNDARIES FOR THE ECOLOGICAL STATUS	20
3.5.1 <i>REFERENCE VALUES</i>	20
3.5.2 <i>CLASS BOUNDARIES</i>	21
3.6 COMPARISON WITH EXISTING BOUNDARIES	25
3.7 TRANSITIONAL RIVERS BELONGING TO TYPE R16	28
3.7.1 <i>OPTION 1: BIOTIC INDEX</i>	28
3.7.2 <i>OPTION 2: M-AMBI</i>	29
3.8 ECOLOGICAL POTENTIAL.....	30
3.8.1 <i>BACKGROUND</i>	30
3.8.2 <i>RIVER TYPES WHERE THE ENVIRONMENTAL OBJECTIVES FOR ES CAN BE MET IN HMWB</i>	31
3.8.3 <i>RIVER TYPES WHERE LOWER ENVIRONMENTAL OBJECTIVES FOR EP THAN FOR ES ARE JUSTIFIED</i>	32
3.8.4 <i>THEORETICAL OPTIONS TO SET BOUNDARIES FOR EP IN THE REFERENCE APPROACH</i>	33
3.8.5 <i>MITIGATION MEASURES OR PRAGUE APPROACH</i>	34
4 LAKES	36
4.1 DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSES OF THE BIOLOGICAL COMMUNITY.....	36
4.2 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN BIOLOGICAL INDICES.....	38
4.3 PROPOSAL OF A MULTIMETRIC INDEX FOR BULGARIAN LAKES (BMMI)	40
4.4 SIGNIFICANT INFLUENCE FACTORS	41
4.4.1 <i>PHYSICAL-CHEMICAL PARAMETERS</i>	41
4.4.2 <i>HYDROMORPHOLOGICAL PRESSURES</i>	41
4.4.3 <i>CORINE LANDCOVER</i>	41
4.5 PRESSURE – RESPONSE RELATIONSHIP	42
4.5.1 <i>PRESSURE INDEX CALCULATION</i>	42

4.5.2	<i>RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PRESSURE INDEX AND BMMI</i>	43
4.6	REFERENCE CONDITIONS AND CLASS BOUNDARIES FOR THE ECOLOGICAL STATUS	45
4.6.1	<i>REFERENCE VALUES</i>	45
4.6.2	<i>CLASS BOUNDARIES</i>	45
4.6.3	<i>TRANSITIONAL LAKES BELONGING TO TYPE L9–L10</i>	46
4.6.4	<i>CONCLUDING REMARK</i>	50
4.7	ECOLOGICAL POTENTIAL.....	51
5	CONCLUSION	52
6	REFERENCES	54
7	DATA ANNEX	57

Abbreviations

AMBI	AZTI's Marine Biotic Index
ASPT	Average Score per Taxon
AWB	Artificial water body
BMMI	Bulgarian multi-metric index for lakes
BMWP	Biological Monitoring Working Party
BQE	Biological quality elements
EPT	Ephemeroptera – Plecoptera – Trichoptera index
EQR	Ecological quality ratio
EU	European Union
GD-EP	General document on ecological potential (Annex 1 of the Final Report)
H'	Shannon index of diversity
HMMI	Hungarian multi-metric index
HMWB	Heavily modified water body
IC	Intercalibration
ITC	Index of trophic completeness
nEQR	Normalised ecological quality ratio
PTI	Pollution tolerance index
RET13	Rhithral feeding type index

Acknowledgements

Thanks to the colleagues who participated in field work as well as in the process of cleaning, sorting and determination of macrozoobenthos samples: Yanka Vidinova, Violeta Tyufekchieva, Mila Ihtimanska, Galia Georgieva, Vesela Evtimova, Milcho Todorov.

1 Introduction and objectives according to the ToR

Benthic macroinvertebrates are one of the biological quality elements (BQE) required for the classification of ecological status and ecological potential of surface water bodies (SWB) under the Water Framework Directive (WFD). It is relevant for lakes/reservoirs and rivers.

Up to now, national classification methods have been developed for all river types except the transitional type R16. Among lakes, a method for ecological status classification based on benthic invertebrates is available only for type L5 with Lake Srebarna as the only representative of this type (Ordinance H4 from 2012, as amended in 2020 (MoEW 2020)).

For some river types and for the lake type L5, the national methods were successfully intercalibrated with methods from other EU member states (MS), which share the comparable types. The results of the intercalibration are summarised in the reports of Wolfram *et al.* (2016a), Wolfram *et al.* (2016b), Birk *et al.* (2016) and Varbiro *et al.* (2016), and officially published in the EU Decision 2018/229/EU (2018).

Activity 6.3 of the ToR requires the development/validation of the classification system for the assessment of the ecological status of river and lake types that have not yet been included in the intercalibration: R1, R3, R5, R9, R10, R11, R12, R13, R14 (without the sub-type, corresponding to the Mediterranean type RM-2), R15, R16, L1, L2, L3, L4, L6, L7, L8, L9, and L10.

This task includes:

- 1) An evaluation of existing classification methods and types to be considered;
- 2) An evaluation of available data on benthic invertebrates and relevant pressures;
- 3) Calculations of pressure-response relationships;
- 4) A definition of reference conditions and reference values for the selected metric(s);
- 5) Setting of class boundaries.

Activity 6.4 of the ToR requires the development of a classification system for the assessment of the ecological potential of heavily modified water bodies of rivers, lakes/reservoirs and transitional waters under the approach adopted by WG ECOSTAT and Water directors (integrated requirements of both CIS WFD approach and Prague approach of "mitigating measures")

2 Available Data on Macroinvertebrates and Pressures

2.1 Monitoring sites

The consolidated data set includes data from 218 monitoring sites belonging to 175 SWB (with up to 3 sites per SWB) sampled between May and November 2020. 79 sites were examined for lakes. The sites represent 19 lake types including 4 types of Black Sea coastal lakes (L07 – L10). The only national lake type not included is L05 with Lake Srebarna as the only representative. This lake types was successfully intercalibrated in 2017 (Borics *et al.* 2018). For the update of the lake typology and changes in the assignment of sites to types see Annex 2 Phytoplankton of the Final Report.

For the rivers, 139 sites were sampled but 7 sites were found to have dried out. The remaining 132 sites were assigned to 14 types including 9 sites in the transitional Black river firths (R16). The following tables show the number of monitoring sites for lakes and rivers per type, category and altitude class (Table 1 to Table 4).

Table 1. Number of monitoring sites available per lake type and category (AWB ... Artificial water body, HMWB ... Heavily modified water body)

Type	AWB	HMWB	Natural
L01		1	4
L02		6	
L03		5	1
L04	1	2	1
L05a			2
L06		1	2
L07		1	3
L08		2	2
L09	1	7	
L10		4	
L11a		1	
L11b		2	
L11c		1	
L12		4	
L13		5	
L14		4	
L15	1	4	
L16	1	4	
L17	1	4	

Table 2. Number of monitoring sites available per river type and category

Type	HMWB	Natural
R01		9
R03	6	10
R04	5	
R05	4	8
R07	5	
R08	4	1
R09	2	6
R10	2	5
R11	8	9
R12	5	8
R13	3	7
R14		9
R15		7
R16	1	8

Table 3. Number of monitoring sites available per lake type and altitude class (in m above sea level).

Type	<200	200–500	500–800	800–1800	>1800
L01					5
L02	1	3	2		
L03				5	1
L04		1	2	1	
L05a	2				
L06	2	1			
L07	4				
L08	4				
L09	8				
L10	4				
L11	2	2		1	
L12	1	3			
L13		1	3	1	
L14	4				
L15	2	3			
L16	2	3			
L17	3	2			

Table 4. Number of monitoring sites available per river type and altitude class (in m above sea level).

Type	<200	200–500	500–800	800–1800	>1800
R01				9	
R03	2	4	7	3	
R04	3	1	1		
R05	3	6	2	1	
R07	5				
R08	5				
R09	3	5			
R10	7				
R11	17				
R12	12	1			
R13	5	3	1	1	
R14	6	2	1		
R15	4	2	1		
R16	9				

2.2 Biological data

The benthic macroinvertebrate collection is performed through an adapted version of the multi-habitat sampling methodology developed on European AQEM/STAR projects (Cheshmedjiev *et al.* 2011; Cheshmedzhiev & Varadinova 2013), in accordance to the standards BDS EN ISO 10870:2012 and EN 16150:2012. The method is regulated by the applicable water legislation Ordinance H-4 from 2012, as amended (MoEW 2020).

In the rivers, benthic macroinvertebrates are collected by wading in the river or along the riparian zone in deep rivers (ca. 100 m). The procedure follows a multi-habitat sampling strategy, where several subsamples from representative habitats are combined to one mixed sample, depending of their relative proportion in the river. The sampling follows the CEN standard EN 16150:2012 (pro-rata multi-habitat sampling of benthic macroinvertebrates from wadable rivers) using a hand net with a mesh size of 500 µm.

In the lakes and reservoirs sampling took place in the littoral zone. Sampling method was comparable to rivers, which means that one composite sample from several substrates was taken.

The large amounts of bottom substrate collected required pre-screening with sieves and primary cleaning of the macrozoobenthos from the substrate on site. The benthic samples were transferred to wide-neck bottles or comparable containers (depending on the amount of material) and preserved in 70% alcohol. The containers were labelled with information about the date and place of sampling.

In the laboratory all macroinvertebrates were sorted and determined using a stereomicroscope. For large samples, subsamples were taken. Benthic taxa were identified at the lowest taxonomic level possible (family level, where possible to species/genus level).

2.3 Biological metrics

In order to identify to most suitable metric, 11 biological indices for lakes and 7 biological indices for rivers were calculated. The calculations were carried out with the help of the software Asterics (<http://www.agem.de/mains/products.php>, accessed on 5 May 2021) in most cases (Table 5). The Biotic Index (based on the Irish biotic index) was calculated by expert judgment in accordance with the methodology for calculation. For AMBI the software from <https://ambi.azti.es/> (accessed on 2 August 2021) was used. The index ITC was calculated using the software MaTros (<http://www.macro.nemi-ekb.ru/index.php?r=site/login&lang=en>, last access on 16 August 2021).

Abbreviations of metrics and indices in Table 5:

Biotic index	BI (when normalised: nBI), see details below
BMWP	Biological Monitoring Working Party (Hawkes 1998)
ASPT	Average Score per Taxon (= BMWB / number of families used for the BMWP)
RET13	Rhithral feeding type index [Rhithraler Ernährungstypen-Index]
Shannon-Index H'	Index of diversity
EPT abundance [%]	Ephemeroptera (mayflies), Plecoptera (stone flies), Trichoptera (caddies flies)
ITC	Index of trophic completeness (Pavluk <i>et al.</i> 2000)
HMMI	Hungarian multi-metric index (Varbiro <i>et al.</i> 2016)
PTI	Pollution tolerance index (Klemm <i>et al.</i> 1990)
AMBI	AZTI's Marine Biotic Index (Borja <i>et al.</i> 2000; Borja <i>et al.</i> 2003)

Table 5. List of available biological indices for lakes and rivers and the total number of samples from lakes or rivers sampled in 2020. *AMBI was calculated only for lakes of type L09 and L10 as well as for rivers of type R16. Abbreviations of indices see text below.

Biological Index	Lakes	Rivers	Software
Number of taxa	79 (79)	132 (132)	Asterics
BI	79 (79)	132 (132)	Excel
EPT abundance [%]	-	132 (132)	Asterics
RET13	-	132 (132)	Asterics
ITC	73 (79)	-	MaTros
Shannon diversity index H'	79 (79)	132 (132)	Asterics
Number of families	79 (79)	-	Asterics
BMWP	79 (79)	132 (132)	Asterics
HMMI	79 (79)	-	Excel + Asterics
ASPT	76 (79)	131 (132)	Asterics
Oligochaete abundance [%]	78 (79)	-	Asterics
PTI	61 (79)	-	Asterics
AMBI	12*	-	AMBI and M-AMBI

The Biotic Index, originally Irish Biotic Index (Q-scheme; McGarrigle & Lucey (2009) is the national method used for the intercalibrated river types R2, R4, R7 and R8. The metric calculation is described in Cheshmedzhiev & Varadinova (2013). The method actually includes two metrics: the total number of taxa and the taxa richness of indicator groups A (very sensitive), B, C, D and E (very tolerant). The individuals are counted, abundance is calculated in abundance classes: few (1–5), present (6–20), common (21–50), plentiful (51–100), dominant (100+). The BI is calculated from the relative proportions of the tolerance groups. Depending on additional criteria, the calculated value can be downgraded.

2.4 Physical-chemical data

In addition to the biological data, physical-chemical data (Table 6) are available from most sampling dates or from sampling dates close to the date of biological sampling. The data included general physical-chemical parameters such as water temperature, electric conductivity, oxygen concentration and saturation, pH, phosphorus and compounds (total phosphorus, orthophosphate [as soluble reactive phosphorus]), nitrogen and compounds (total nitrogen, ammonium, nitrate, nitrite), and biological oxygen demand BOD₅. Detailed analyses on these parameters are shown in Annex 2 Phytoplankton and Annex 3 Phytobenthos of the Final Report.

Table 6. List of available physical-chemical parameters (abbreviation in brackets) for lakes and rivers and the total number of samples from the campaign 2020.

Parameter	Lakes	Rivers
Water temperature (WT)	76 (79)	132 (132)
pH	77 (79)	132 (132)
Electric conductivity (EC)	77 (79)	132 (132)
Dissolved oxygen (DO)	77 (79)	132 (132)
Oxygen saturation (O ₂ -sat)	77 (79)	132 (132)
Biological oxygen demand (BOD ₅)	79 (79)	132 (132)
Total nitrogen (TN)	79 (79)	132 (132)
Ammonium-nitrogen (NH ₄ -N)	79 (79)	132 (132)
Nitrite-nitrogen (NO ₂ -N)	79 (79)	132 (132)
Nitrate-nitrogen (NO ₃ -N)	79 (79)	131 (132)
Orthophosphate-P = soluble reactive P (SRP)	79 (79)	132 (132)
Total phosphorus (TP)	79 (79)	132 (132)

2.5 Hydromorphological Pressures

Table 7 shows the pressures used from lakes and rivers for the evaluation of the pressure – response relationships. Details on the hydromorphological pressures have been presented earlier as Annex 1 of the 5th Bimonthly Progress Report (*cf* chapter 2.3.3 in the Final Report). In the pressure – response relationships, both single metrics and the sum of all pressures (abbreviated below as SUM_Pres), and weighted combinations of different pressures were tested.

Table 7. List of used hydromorphological pressures for lakes and rivers at the sampling site (in brackets: abbreviations used below).

Parameter	Lakes	Rivers
Impoundment		+
Abstraction		+
Hydropeaking		+
Channelisation		+
Lateral dams at the sampling site (Dams_site)		+
Alteration of riparian vegetation at the sampling site (VegRip)	+	+
Habitat alteration at the sampling site (HabAlt)	+	+
(Assumed) toxic impact (Toxic)	+	+
Water level fluctuations	+	
Aquaculture	+	
General physical-chemical impact (Anth_pres_ph_ch)	+	+
General impact from land use (Anth_pres_land)	+	+

2.6 Corine Landcover

From the Corine landcover (CLC) data that were available on the basis of the SWB, the CLC class 1 (artificial) as well as the intensive and extensive agriculture in the catchment area was used, in all cases as relative proportion of the total area of the SWB watershed.

3 Rivers

3.1 Descriptive analyses of the biological community

To identify general patterns in the macroinvertebrate assemblages, a similarity analysis was carried out using non-metric multidimensional scaling (nMDS). The Anosim-test was used for categorical data to determine if the differences between two or more groups are significant. The calculations were carried out in R (R Core Team 2021) using the package *vegan* (Oksanen *et al.* 2020). Indicator species analyses helped to detect indicator taxa for special types. For this the R package called *indicspecies* (Cáceres *et al.* 2010) was used.

NMDS is an indirect gradient analysis approach which produces an ordination based on a distance or dissimilarity matrix. Unlike methods which attempt to maximise the variance or correspondence between objects in an ordination (*e.g.*, correspondence analysis, principal components analysis), nMDS attempts to represent, as closely as possible, the pairwise dissimilarity between objects in a low-dimensional space (usually 2-dimensional). NMDS is a rank-based approach. This means that the original distance data is substituted with ranks, which makes it robust to data which do not have an identifiable distribution (non-parametric). NMDS tolerates missing pairwise distances and can be used for quantitative, semi-quantitative, qualitative, or mixed variables. In our analyses, we used the raw data with all taxa identified to the lowest taxonomical level (often species/genus, but in several cases also family) and with the raw individual numbers. Bray-Curtis was used as distance measure.

The nMDS plotted in the following two figures show the similarity of all samples from rivers based on their species assemblage and individual counts, in Figure 1 grouped by altitude class, in Figure 2 grouped by national river type. There is large overlap of the sample similarity irrespective of altitude, although samples from the lowland and from mountain regions (>800 m asl) seem separate in most cases (with 1 outlier) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. nMDS plot on macroinvertebrates abundance data in BG rivers (+ transitional type R16), grouped by altitude class. Database: sampling campaigns 2020.

Also when grouped by type, no clear separation could be found. Types which show least similarity with other types are R01 (high altitude rivers) and R16 (transitional). There is no overlap also among other types such as R05 *versus* R09 and R11. Overall, benthic invertebrates reflect typology to some extent but other factors (pressure, local conditions) have an influence on the community as well. The relevance of typology is underpinned by the ANOSIM analysis, which allows identifying significant underlying factors. As shown in Table 8, geographical differences, river type and altitude turned out to have a significant influence on the distribution of sites in the nMDS plot. However, the category natural vs HMWB seems to be too coarse to separate samples/sites.

Figure 2. nMDS plot on macroinvertebrates abundance data (species, single sampling dates) in BG rivers (+ transitional type R16), grouped by Type. Database: sampling campaigns 2020.

Table 8. Results of the Anosim statistics with the R-value and the significance values.

Grouping	R	p	Significance
River basin district	0.1359	<0.001	***
River type	0.3149	<0.001	***
Freshwater/transitional water *	0.3899	<0.001	***
Category (natural/HMWB)	-0.0433	0.9405	
Altitude class	0.161	<0.001	***

3.2 Relationship between biological indices

The correlation among the most important metrics are shown in Figure 3 and Table 9. The metrics were normalised (to 0–1) to exclude possible bias due to different scaling. For abbreviations see chapter 2.3.

The clear and significant correlation illustrates that it would be redundant to define a multi-metric index based on several indices. Besides, it may make little difference which of these metrics should be selected. The pressure – response relationships will show whether different indices and metrics differ in terms of their response to anthropogenic pressure.

Figure 3. Correlation analysis of important biological indices with indication of the Spearman correlation coefficient. Significant correlations are indicated by red stars. For abbreviations see chapter 2.3.

Table 9. Results of the Mantel-test between macroinvertebrate community and biological indices. For abbreviations see chapter 2.3.

Indices	Correlation r	p	Significance
BI	0.321	<0.001	***
BMWP	0.128	<0.001	***
ASPT	0.356	<0.001	***
RET1 3	0.269	<0.001	***
Taxa richness	0.079	0.05	*
Shannon-Index H'	0.211	<0.001	***

3.3 Significant impact factors

To find significant correlations between pressures (land use, hydromorphological pressures, hydro-chemical data) and biological indices, a Mantel-test was carried out. The calculations were carried out in R (R Core Team 2021) using the package vegan (Oksanen *et al.* 2020).

3.3.1 Physical-chemical parameters

The Mantel test based on the non-parametric Spearman correlation coefficient was applied on the nMDS results to identify whether selected environmental factors have a significant explanatory power on the similarity of the sites in the nMDS plot. Both conductivity, nutrients, and chemical variables indicating organic pollution (BOD₅, NH₄-N) turned out to be significantly correlated (Table 10). They also showed a significant negative correlation in a direct correlation analysis with the Biotic index BI (Table 11).

Table 10. Results of the Mantel-test based on the Spearman rank correlation between macroinvertebrate community and selected chemical parameters (abbreviations see Table 6).

Indices	Correlation R	p	Significance
EC	0.324	<0.001	***
BOD ₅	0.169	<0.001	***
TP	0.162	<0.001	***
NH ₄ -N	0.102	<0.05	*

Table 11. Spearman correlation coefficients between selected physical-chemical parameters (abbreviations see Table 6) and the Biotic Index BI.

Parameter	Spearman correlation r	p	Significance
EC	-0.550	<0.001	***
NH ₄ -N	-0.513	<0.001	***
NO ₃ -N	-0.390	<0.001	***
TP	-0.646	<0.001	***
SRP	-0.559	<0.001	***
BOD ₅	-0.320	<0.001	***

3.3.2 Hydromorphological pressures

Similar to the physical-chemical parameters, also the hydromorphological pressure variables showed a significant correlation within the nMDS (using the Mantel test) and in direct correlation analysis with BI (Table 12, Table 13).

Table 12. Results of the Mantel-test based on the Spearman rank correlation between macroinvertebrate communities and selected hydromorphological pressures. For abbreviations see Table 7.

Indices	Correlation R	p	Significance
Sum of all pressures (AnthSum)	0.141	<0.001	***
VegRip	0.141	<0.001	***
HabAlt	0.104	<0.001	***
Anth_pres_land	0.080	<0.001	***
Anth_pres_ph_ch	0.115	<0.001	***

Table 13. Spearman-correlation coefficient between the hydromorphological pressures and the Biotic Index BI. For abbreviations see Table 7.

Physical-chemical parameter	Spearman correlation	p	significance
Impoundment	0.003	0.974	ns
Hydropeaking	0.073	0.409	ns
Abstraction	-0.139	0.114	ns
Dams_site	-0.051	0.561	ns
Channelisation	-0.321	<0.001	***
VegRip	-0.458	<0.001	***
HabAlt	-0.416	<0.001	***
Toxic	-0.273	<0.001	***
Anth_pres_land	-0.477	<0.001	***
Anth_pres_ph_ch	-0.481	<0.001	***
SUM_Press	-0.539	<0.001	***

3.3.3 Corine landcover (CLC)

Another analysis focused on land use and again the similarity in the nMDS could be significantly correlated with the three CLC classes, which were also directly correlated with the Biotic Index (Table 14 & Table 15).

Table 14. Results of the Mantel-test based on the Spearman rank correlation between macroinvertebrate community and Corine landcover.

Indices	Correlation R	p	Significance
CLC1	0.107	<0.01	**
CLC_AgrExtensive	0.091	<0.01	**
CLC_AgrIntensive	0.264	<0.001	***

Table 15. Spearman-correlation coefficients between the Corine landcover and the Biotic Index BI

Physical-chemical parameter	Spearman correlation	p	significance
CLC 1	-0.375	<0.001	***
CLC AgrIntensive	-0.391	<0.001	***
CLC AgrExtensive	-0.215	<0.05	*

Concluding, the data indicate that the biological response metrics – and especially the BI which is already used in the intercalibrated river types – are sensitive against different anthropogenic pressures.

3.4 Pressure – Response Relationship

3.4.1 Pressure Index calculation

The pressure index (PI) included the sum of all hydromorphological pressures and selected chemical parameters (EC, TP, NO₃-N, BOD₅). The selected parameters were chosen by evaluating their significance in the correlation with the biological response metrics.

As the different pressure have different scales, the PI was calculated as the sum of the *normalized* values of these stressor variables. The normalization was not carried in the statistical sense (by subtracting the mean and dividing by the standard deviation) but as commonly applied in the IC exercise, which is by reducing the range of most values to 0–1. This was done by defining anchor points (here: 10th and 90th percentiles):

$$x^* = \frac{P_{10} - x}{P_{10} - P_{90}}$$

x* = normalized value

x = raw value

P10, P90 = 10th and 90th percentile

As the percentiles and not the maximum are chosen as anchor points, some values below 10th percentile and above 90th percentile have normalized values which are below 0 or above 1. The majority of the pressure data, however, is within the same range. For the electric conductivity, type-specific anchor points were used for the transitional river type R16 and the remaining (freshwater) rivers.

The PI is thus calculated as follows:

$$PI = \text{Sum. of pressures}^* + TP^* + NO_3^* + BOD_5^* + EC^*$$

3.4.2 Relationship between pressure index and Biotic Index BI

Various biological metrics were tested in the pressure – response relationships. As they did not differ very much as regards significance and explanatory power (R²), we decided to use the Biotic index, which was used in the IC exercise, also for types not yet intercalibrated. The pressure – response relationship with PI as independent variable and BI as dependent variable is shown in Figure 4. With R² >0.4 (which corresponds to a correlation coefficient of 0.63), the regression model exceeds the recommended *r* value according to the CIS Guidance Documents on IC. The outcome of the regression model is shown in Table 16.

Figure 4. Correlation between the pressure index and the Biotic index BI.

Table 16. Linear regression model Pressure Index PI vs Biotic Index BI.

Linear regression model: Biotic Index BI ~ Pressure Index PI

Call:

lm(formula = BI ~ PI, data = pc)

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1.87375	-0.34058	0.06062	0.37536	1.26869

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	4.18169	0.08270	50.566	< 2e-16 ***
PI	-0.25243	0.02743	-9.203	7.99e-16 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.615 on 129 degrees of freedom

(1 observation deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.3963, Adjusted R-squared: 0.3917

F-statistic: 84.7 on 1 and 129 DF, p-value: 7.99e-16

The plot in Figure 4 does not yet take into account systematic bias in this relationship in different river types. It may be possible though that the biological response differs between types at the same level of pressure. In addition, even in no-pressure situation the BI may be significantly differ between high-mountain and lowland rivers. This is the reason why type-specific classification methods are required. To cope with this problem, a linear mixed model was developed to identify type-specific shifts in the overall regression model. This statistical tool was developed based on the experience of

the first round of IC that many types lack sites in reference conditions (Mischke *et al.* 2016; Wolfram *et al.* 2016a). Using linear mixed models allows calculating so-called offsets for different types (Willby *et al.* 2014). In the IC process, this statistical procedure was also called “continuous benchmarking” (Böhmer *et al.* 2011).

In brief, this method allows combining sections of different regression lines into one model. Theoretically, these differences in the regression lines may be due to different slopes or different intercepts. During the intercalibration process in other Geographical Intercalibration Groups, it was generally assumed that the regressions differed in intercept only, but not in slope. The linear mixed model was used to calculate the differences of these intercepts or offsets. The calculations were carried out in *R* with the package *lme4* (Bates *et al.* 2015; Bates *et al.* 2012).

The plot in Figure 4 follows the general regression model

```
lm1 <- lm (BI ~ PI)
```

where PI is a fixed factor. Including *type* as random factor (variable intercept, fixed slope), the regression model looks like:

```
lm2 <- lmer (BI ~ PI + (1|Type))
```

The plot with offset-corrected BI – *i.e.* BI after continuous benchmarking, thereafter named *cbBI* – is shown in Figure 5. The fit for the model R^2 improves slightly from 0.4 to 0.5. The linear regression model

```
lm1 <- lm (cbBI ~ PI)
```

is summarised in Table 18. Table 19 gives the calculated offsets per type.

Table 17. Linear mixed model with Pressure Index as fixed variable and type as random factor.

Linear mixed model fit by REML ['lmerMod']

```
Call:
lmer (BI ~ PI + (1 | Type), data = pc)

REML criterion at convergence: 233

Scaled residuals:
   Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-3.3283 -0.5611  0.1700  0.6272  1.9848

Random effects:
 Groups Name      Variance Std.Dev.
 Type   (Intercept) 0.1184   0.3441
 Residual                0.2805   0.5296
Number of obs: 131, groups: Type, 14

Fixed effects:
              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  4.23288    0.12307  34.393  <.0001
PI           -0.25760    0.02771  -9.297  <.0001

Correlation of Fixed Effects:
(Intercept)
PI -0.531
```


Figure 5. Correlation between the pressure index and the cbBI (offset-corrected BI).

Table 18. Linear regression model Pressure Index PI vs cbBI.

Linear regression model: corrected Biotic Index BI ~ Pressure Index PI

Call:

lm(formula = cbBI ~ PI, data = df2)

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1.76265	-0.29715	0.09003	0.33216	1.05116

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	4.23288	0.06839	61.89	<2e-16 ***
PI	-0.25760	0.02268	-11.36	<2e-16 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.5086 on 129 degrees of freedom
(1 observation deleted due to missingness)

Multiple R-squared: 0.4999, Adjusted R-squared: 0.4961

F-statistic: 129 on 1 and 129 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Table 19. Type-specific offsets calculated to derive the cbBI in BG river types (rounded to 3 digits).

Type	Offset	Type	Offset	Type	Offset
R01	0.588	R09	0.363	R14	-0.159
R03	-0.072	R10	-0.110	R15	-0.105
R04	0.141	R11	-0.138	R16	-0.608
R05	-0.126	R12	-0.157	R15	-0.181
R07	0.093	R13	-0.136	R16	-0.657
R08	0.425				

The analysis shows that the benthic communities react on pressures on hydro-morphology, organic pollution and eutrophication in different ways in different river types.

3.5 Reference conditions and class boundaries for the ecological status

3.5.1 Reference values

In the early phase of IC, it was assumed (and required) to derive reference conditions type by type. The WFD and CIS Guidance No 10 (EU Commission 2003) offer different options to achieve this goal:

- Spatially based reference conditions using data from monitoring sites;
- Reference conditions based on predictive modelling;
- Temporally based reference conditions using either historical data or paleoreconstruction or a combination of both;
- A combination of the above approaches.

During the first phase of IC it became clear that sites in reference conditions are lacking in many types and also in BG, many river types do not include stretches and sites which are in high status. This made it necessary to develop new approaches such as the concept of alternative benchmarks (representing for instance the good/moderate boundary) or continuous benchmarking as described above. It allows to enlarge the number of sites from which benchmark values can be derived.

A prerequisite of both approaches is the definition of reference or benchmark criteria which allow defining conditions under which sites are expected to represent reference or benchmark status. For the BG rivers, the following combination was defined:

- No HMWB
- Sum of hygro pressures <4
- BOD₅ ≤2 mg L⁻¹
- CLC Class 1 (Artificial) ≤2%
- CLC Intensive agriculture ≤10%

Based on these criteria, 17 sites could be identified and were considered as candidate reference sites (Table 20; R16 not included – see chapter 3.7). It must be stressed that the section aims at developing the classification system but does not necessarily mean that all these sites truly represent reference conditions.

Similar to approaches in various Geographical Intercalibration Groups in the IC exercise, the median of cbBI in this group of sites was defined as reference value

- Reference value (median): cbBI = 4.412

For the H/G boundary, various percentiles were used in the IC exercise, often the 10th percentile, which would result in a class boundary of 4.13. When compared to the already intercalibrated BI values, this value seems too strict. Therefore, a cbBI of 4 was accepted as H/G boundary; it lies between the minimum value of the selected sites (3.9) and the 5th percentile (4.09).

- H/G boundary (10th percentile): cbBI = 4.0

The H/G boundary corresponds to an ecological quality ratio EQR of 0.94.

Based on these two values and using the offsets as defined above, we can calculate type-specific reference values and H/G class boundaries, as shown further below.

Table 20. Candidate reference sites identified based on reference criteria (see text).

SiteCode	River	Site	Type	CLC 1	CLC AgrInt	BOD ₅	Sum Pr	cbBI
BG4ST06564MS403	r. Slavova	river water intake	R01	0.0%	0.0%	0.78	0	3.91
BG4ST06669MS401	r. Otovitsa	after Otovitsa Hut	R01	0.0%	0.0%	0.63	1	4.41
BG4ST06582MS405	r. Iliina	before the estuary of Rilska River	R01	0.3%	0.0%	0.63	1	4.41
BG4ST06569MS402	r. Blagoevgradska Bistritsa	after Bodrost area, before Slavova River	R01	0.0%	0.0%	1.40	0	4.41
BG4ST06569MS401	r. Blagoevgradska Bistritsa	"Kartalska polyana" Meadow	R01	0.0%	0.0%	1.40	0	4.41
BG4ST65149MS401	r. Sandanska Bistritsa	below Popina Luka	R01	0.0%	0.0%	0.79	0	4.41
BG4ST65341MS401	r. Vlahinska	before Sinanishka River inflow near Vlahi village	R01	0.0%	0.0%	1.32	1	4.41
BG4ST65891MS402	r. Rilska	before Rila Monastery	R01	0.3%	0.0%	0.63	0	4.41
BG4ME47389MS403	r. Retidzhe	before HPP 1	R01	0.0%	0.0%	1.44	1	4.41
BG4ME47521MS401	r. Bezbozhka	before estuary, bridge on the road to Gotse Delchev	R03	0.0%	0.3%	2.00	0	5.07
BG3TU00999MS0380	r. Tundzha	Panitsite area, summer camp	R03	0.2%	1.2%	1.01	1	5.07
BG2IU76411MS410	r. Karaagach	v. Fazanovo	R11	0.1%	5.9%	1.27	1	4.14
BG2RE00219MS255	r. Silistar	upstream delta, bridge on the Rezovo - Sinemorets road	R11	0.0%	0.1%	0.00	0	4.14
BG4ST00632MS601	r. Mochura	Stefanov vrah	R13	0.0%	0.0%	1.00	1	4.64
BG4ST65371MS720	r. Ludata	at Yanovski bridge after Senokos site	R14	0.0%	0.0%	1.69	0	4.16
BG3AR00661MS0206	r. Chataldjevitsa	delta under the wall of Borovitsa Dam	R14	0.5%	4.3%	1.10	1	5.16
BG3MA0B112MSB002	r. Luda	before confluence in Byala river	R14	1.7%	8.7%	1.33	2	4.16

CLC 1 = % of CLC class Artificial, CLC AgrInt = % of CLC classes intensive agriculture, BOD₅ = biological oxygen demand, Sum Pr = sum of hygro pressures, cbBI = benchmarked Biotic Index.

3.5.2 Class boundaries

The CIS Guidance No 14 (EU Commission 2011) gives advice and suggests several steps how to set class boundaries for the ecological status. To reach this level, it must be proven that the metric (in our case: the cbBI) shows a relationship with the impact gradient represented in the data set (Step 1 of the CIS Guidance). This was done in chapter 3.4.2.

Step 1

Figure 6. Step 1 of the Boundary Setting procedure of CIS Guidance No 14.

Step 2 is to identify if there are any discontinuities in the relationship between the metric and the gradient of impact represented by the data set (Figure 7).

Step 2

Figure 7. Step 2 of the Boundary Setting procedure of CIS Guidance No 14.

If there are no discontinuities, it must be assessed whether class centres or class boundaries can be located using paired metrics (Step 3). If yes, it should be determined whether values derived from the paired metric analysis correspond to class centres or class boundaries.

Step 3

Figure 8. Step 3 of the Boundary Setting procedure of CIS Guidance No 14.

Neither any discontinuity in the relationship between pressure and the impact nor a paired metric analysis were helpful to set the boundaries for the status classes. Following the Boundary Setting Protocol of EU Commission (2011), the continuum of impact can finally be divided into equal width classes (Step 4).

Step 4

Figure 9. Step 4 of the Boundary Setting procedure of CIS Guidance No 14.

Based on the type-specific reference values and H/G boundaries, and with BI = 1 as lowest possible value of the metric, the further boundaries are derived from the equal distance approach.

The final step helps to normalise¹ the *EQR* values in order to define H/G as 0.8, G/M as 0.6, M/P as 0.4 and P/B as 0.2.

The following algorithms are used to transform *EQR* values to *nEQR* values:

EQR_i	$nEQR_i$
$\geq EQR_{H/G}$	$(EQR_i - EQR_{H/G}) / (1 - EQR_{H/G}) * 0.2 + 0.8$ <i>if $nEQR_i > 1$, then $nEQR_i$ is set to 1</i>
$EQR_{H/G} > EQR_i \geq EQR_{G/M}$	$(EQR_i - EQR_{G/M}) / (EQR_{H/G} - EQR_{G/M}) * 0.2 + 0.6$
$EQR_{G/M} > EQR_i \geq EQR_{M/P}$	$(EQR_i - EQR_{M/P}) / (EQR_{G/M} - EQR_{M/P}) * 0.2 + 0.4$
$EQR_{M/P} > EQR_i \geq EQR_{P/B}$	$(EQR_i - EQR_{P/B}) / (EQR_{M/P} - EQR_{P/B}) * 0.2 + 0.2$
$< EQR_{P/B}$	$(EQR_i - EQR_{min}) / (EQR_{P/B} - EQR_{min}) * 0.2$

Each class includes the lower class boundary (e.g. $nEQR = 0.8 \rightarrow$ high status). Per definitionem, *nEQR* values >1 are fixed at 1, while values <0 are fixed at 0.

Table 21 summarises the type-specific BI values, *EQR* and *nEQR* values.

Table 21. Type-specific values for the Biotic Index BI in Bulgarian rivers (excluding Danube R6 and transitional R16).

	R01	R03	R04	R05	R07	R08	R09	R10	R11	R12	R13	R14	R15	
offset	0.588	-0.072		-0.126			0.363	-0.11	-0.138	-0.157	-0.136		-0.105	
cbBI	BI													
Reference	4.412	5.00	4.34	4.55	4.29	4.51	4.84	4.78	4.30	4.27	4.26	4.28	4.25	4.31
H/G	4.000	4.59	3.93	4.14	3.87	4.09	4.43	4.36	3.89	3.86	3.84	3.86	3.84	3.90
G/M		3.69	3.20	3.36	3.15	3.32	3.57	3.52	3.17	3.15	3.13	3.15	3.13	3.18
M/P		2.80	2.47	2.57	2.44	2.55	2.72	2.68	2.45	2.43	2.42	2.43	2.42	2.45
P/B		1.90	1.73	1.79	1.72	1.77	1.86	1.84	1.72	1.72	1.71	1.72	1.71	1.73
lowest		1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
nEQR	EQR													
Reference	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
H/G	0.80	0.92	0.91	0.91	0.90	0.91	0.92	0.91	0.90	0.90	0.90	0.90	0.90	0.90
G/M	0.60	0.74	0.74	0.74	0.73	0.74	0.74	0.74	0.74	0.74	0.73	0.74	0.74	0.74
M/P	0.40	0.56	0.57	0.56	0.57	0.57	0.56	0.56	0.57	0.57	0.57	0.57	0.57	0.57
P/B	0.20	0.38	0.40	0.39	0.40	0.39	0.38	0.38	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.40
lowest	0.00	0.20	0.23	0.22	0.23	0.22	0.21	0.21	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.24	0.23

¹ The normalisation as carried out here is not a normalisation in a strict statistical sense, which is calculated by subtracting the mean and dividing through the standard deviation. Nevertheless, the term “normalisation” has been introduced in the IC exercise is commonly used to set *EQR* values at fixed values in 0.2 intervals.

3.6 Comparison with existing boundaries

As pointed out earlier, the procedure to derive reference values and class boundaries in the previous chapters followed the CIS Guidance on IC and was carried out, in a first step, irrespective of existing boundaries as defined in the national ordinance H-4 form 2012, as amended in 2020 (MoEW 2020) and – for some types – as included in the Decision 2018/229/EU (2018).

In this section we compare the outcome of the analysis and evaluate whether the existing boundaries are supported or can be accepted by our analyses, or whether they should be amended.

Table 21 lists the ranges of the Biotic Index for all national river types (except R6 Danube and R16 transitional). The reference values are not included in the legal documents, but can be derived from the EQR values. For R07, R08 and R14b, there were taken from the IC reports from 2016 (Wolfram *et al.* 2016a; b).

The subsequent Table 23 gives the same information in a different form. Since the BI can only have discrete values in 0.5 intervals, all possible values can be listed and assigned to a status class. The classes of ecological status are marked in colours. The right panel of this table shows the corresponding EQR values.

Table 22. Ranges of Biotic Index (BI) values to assess the ecological status of Bulgarian rivers according to the ordinance H-4 (MoEW 2020) and the Decision 2018/229/EU (2018).

Type	Reference	High	Good	Moderate	Poor	Bad
R01	5.0	4.5–5.0	4.0	2.5–3.5	2.0	1.0–1.5
R02	5.2	4.5–5.0	3.5–4.0	2.5–3.0	2.0	1.0–1.5
R03	5.2	4.5–5.0	3.5–4.0	2.5–3.0	2.0	1.0–1.5
R04	5.2	4.5–5.0	3.5–4.0	2.5–3.0	2.0	1.0–1.5
R05	5.2	4.5–5.0	3.5–4.0	2.5–3.0	2.0	1.0–1.5
R07	4.8	4.0–5.0	3.5	2.5–3.0	2.0	1.0–1.5
R08	4.8	4.0–5.0	3.5	2.5–3.0	2.0	1.0–1.5
R09	3.5	3.5–4.0	3.0	2.0–2.5	1.5	1.0
R10	5.0	4.0	3.5	2.5–3.0	2.0	1.0–1.5
R11	3.5	3.5–4.0	3.0	2.0–2.5	1.5	1.0
R12	5.0	4.0–4.5	3.5	2.5–3.0	2.0	1.0–1.5
R13	5.0	4.0–4.5	3.5	2.5–3.0	2.0	1.0–1.5
R14a	3.5	3.5–4.0	3.0	2.0–2.5	1.5	1.0
R14b	4.96	4.0–5.0	3.5	2.5–3.0	2.0	1.0–1.5
R14c	3.5	3.5–4.0	3.0	2.0–2.5	1.5	1.0
R15	3.5	3.5–4.0	3.0	2.0–2.5	1.5	1.0

Table 23. Values of Biotic Index (BI) and EQR values for rivers in the legal documents Ordinance H-4 (MoEW 2020) and Decision 2018/229/EU (2018), with corresponding ecological status classes shown in colours: blue = high, green = good, yellow = moderate, orange = poor, red = bad status.

Type	Biotic Index								EQR									
R01	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	1.000	0.900	0.800	0.700	0.600	0.500	0.400	0.300	0.200
R02	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	0.962	0.865	0.769	0.673	0.577	0.481	0.385	0.288	0.192
R03	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	0.962	0.865	0.769	0.673	0.577	0.481	0.385	0.288	0.192
R04	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	0.962	0.865	0.769	0.673	0.577	0.481	0.385	0.288	0.192
R05	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	0.962	0.865	0.769	0.673	0.577	0.481	0.385	0.288	0.192
R07	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	1.042	0.938	0.833	0.729	0.625	0.521	0.417	0.313	0.208
R08	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	1.042	0.938	0.833	0.729	0.625	0.521	0.417	0.313	0.208
R09			4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0			1.143	1.000	0.857	0.714	0.571	0.429	0.286
R10			4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0			0.800	0.700	0.600	0.500	0.400	0.300	0.200
R11			4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0			1.143	1.000	0.857	0.714	0.571	0.429	0.286
R12		4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0		0.900	0.800	0.700	0.600	0.500	0.400	0.300	0.200
R13		4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0		0.900	0.800	0.700	0.600	0.500	0.400	0.300	0.200
R14a			4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0			1.143	1.000	0.857	0.714	0.571	0.429	0.286
R14b	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	1.008	0.907	0.806	0.706	0.605	0.504	0.403	0.302	0.202
R14c			4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0			1.143	1.000	0.857	0.714	0.571	0.429	0.286
R15			4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0			1.143	1.000	0.857	0.714	0.571	0.429	0.286

To compare the outcome of the calculations in chapter 3.5.2 with the values defined in existing legal documents, the continuous BI values calculated in the previous chapter and summarised in Table 21 are assigned to discrete BI values and ecological classes. As shown in Table 24, the outcome is comparable with the existing values, but deviations occur:

- The boundaries identical in the river types R4, R10, R12 and R13. The calculations in this report, which follow the procedures as described in the CIS Guidance Documents and which are based on new data set, support the existing boundaries.
- For river types R3 and R5, the new calculations would suggest a less strict assessment at the H/G boundary than as defined in the Ordinance H-4. This slight difference does not justify changing the existing boundaries, which are more precautionary in the transition between High and Good status.
- For river types R1, R7 and R8, the new calculations would suggest a stricter assessment at the H/G boundary than as defined in the Ordinance H-4. As the types R7 and R8 have been successfully intercalibrated, the values shall not be changed. Although it is possible to define stricter class boundaries than intercalibrated with MS sharing the same GIG type, we do not recommend to do this here. The dataset used in our calculations for these river types is smaller than the one used in the IC project from 2016. Considering the natural variability and methodological uncertainties as well as the allowed range among MS and within an GIG type, the existing boundaries for R7 and R8 should remain as they are. This is justified considering that the most critical boundary G/M is identical in the IC exercise and as suggested by the new calculations. For R1, we also propose not changing the existing boundaries, as also here the G/M boundary is identical and only H/G and M/P would be set higher.
- Stricter boundaries than as defined in the Ordinance H-4 are suggested by our calculations for the river types R9, R11, R14a, R14c and R15. Based on a plausibility check the existing

boundaries in the Ordinance H-4 for the types R9 and R11 seem not sufficiently strict and precautionary. They would result in high status for most sampling sites from 2020 in these two types. Therefore, we recommend changing the boundaries for these two types in the national legal documents (Table 24).

Also the boundaries for R14a, R14c and R15 should be stricter. In the dataset from the sampling campaign 2020, six R14 sites are high and one is moderate both with the existing and the new classification, whereas two sites would get worse (1 moderate > poor, 1 high > good). Among R15, four sites are high status both with the existing and the new classification, while three would get worse (2 good > moderate, 1 high > good)

- No new data from the campaign 2020 are available for the river types R2 and R14b. Both types are successfully intercalibrated.

Table 24. Values of Biotic Index (BI) for rivers as calculated in this project, with corresponding ecological status classes shown in colours: blue = high, green = good, yellow = moderate, orange = poor, red = bad status. The last two columns compare the outcome with the boundaries in the national Ordinance H-4 and give a recommendation on keeping or changing the existing boundaries.

Type	Biotic index								Difference to H-4	Recommendation	
R01	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	stricter at H/G and M/P	keep existing boundaries
R03	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	less strict at H/G	keep existing boundaries
R04	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	identical	keep existing boundaries
R05	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	less strict at H/G	keep existing boundaries
R07	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	stricter	keep existing boundaries
R08	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	stricter	keep existing boundaries
R09	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	stricter	adapt
R10	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	identical	keep existing boundaries
R11	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	stricter	adapt
R12	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	identical	keep existing boundaries
R13	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	identical	keep existing boundaries
R14a	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	stricter	adapt
R14c	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	stricter	adapt
R15	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	stricter	adapt

Concluding, we recommend:

- leaving the existing (partly intercalibrated) class boundaries for the BI unchanged in the river types R1, R2, R3, R4, R5, R7, R8, R10, R12, R13 and R14b;
- defining stricter boundaries for the river types R9, R11, R14a, R14c and R15

A list of all monitoring sites sampled in 2020 with the proposed classification results is given in the data Annex in chapter 7.

3.7 Transitional rivers belonging to type R16

In this project, we tested two approaches:

- i) the BI as described above for freshwater river types
- ii) the M-AMBI*_(n) as described for the transitional lake types L9 and L10.

This section includes only the method proposal for the BI. The M-AMBI*_(n) – and a recommendation of the final method – will be included in the final report.

3.7.1 Option 1: Biotic Index

As shown above (e.g. Figure 4), the transitional rivers belonging to type R16 were included in the analysis of BI in the freshwater river types, although in the BI calculation a adaptation was made to account for slowly flowing waters. As the pressure index included only hydromorphological alterations and organic / nutrient pollution, the assessment based on the BI can only take these stressors into account, whereas alterations of other pressures such as alterations of salinity (change of brackish to purely freshwater systems, hypersalinization) are not considered.

As no or not sufficient R16 reference sites are available to calculate reference values using the spatial approach of the CIS Guidance documents, the overall analysis on all river types and the linear benchmarking approach was used for R16 in the same way as for the other types. Following the same algorithms, an offset of –0.608 was calculated, leading to a reference value of 3.80. Also the class boundary setting was used in the same way as described above for the other river types (Table 21). The continuous-benchmarked reference value of BI (cbBI) and the class boundaries calculated in this way are:

	cbBI	BI	EQR	nEQR
Reference	4.412	3.80	1.00	1.00
H/G	4.000	3.39	0.89	0.80
G/M		2.79	0.73	0.60
M/P		2.20	0.58	0.40
P/B		1.60	0.42	0.20
lowest		1.00	0.26	0.00

Accordingly, the non-continuous BI values are:

Type	Biotic Index								EQR									
R16	5.0	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.053	0.921	0.789	0.658	0.526	0.395	0.263

The classification results of the R16 sites sampled in 2020 are summarised in the next section together with the results from option 2 (Table 25).

3.7.2 Option 2: M-AMBI

The M-AMBI calculation was possible for most sites belonging to type R16. One site with unplausible data was skipped. The very low M-AMBI value might be due to the fact that predominantly freshwater (though salt-tolerant) species were present which hampered applying an index developed for brackish or coastal waters.

Table 25 shows the classification results using the BI (adapted for slow-flowing rivers/river stretches) and the M-AMBI, both expressed as normalised EQR. The discrepancy of the classification result is obvious. Both nEQR correlate with the pressure index (Figure 10), but M-AMBI performs better (after exclusion of one outlier in an expert plausibility check). The direct correlation is weak and not significant ($r_{\text{spearman}} = 0.37$, $p = 0.369$).

Table 25. Outcome of classification results using two options (BI and M-AMBI) for the assessment of transitional rivers belonging to type R16.

Site Code	SWB Code	Site Name	PI	BI	nEQR BI	nEQR M-AMBI
BG2IU07211MS404	BG2IU200R1005	Ropotamo River - before estuary, bridge on E 87	0.99	2.5	0.50	0.75
BG2IU00081MS254	BG2IU800R1115	Lisovo Dere River (Izgrevsko Dere) - estuary, Tsarevo	1.20	3.5	0.86	0.70
BG2IU200R005RP14	BG2IU200R1005	Ropotamo River in MR "Veliov Vir"	0.91	3	0.67	0.62
BG2IU6915MS002	BG2IU600R1013	Karaagach River - estuary	3.35	2.5	0.50	0.45
BG2SE00219MS228	BG2SE200R1101	Fandakliyska River - estuary	2.23	2	0.33	0.43
BG2SE81MS008	BG2SE800R020	Aheloy River - Camping Aheloy	3.56	3.5	0.86	0.46
BG2VE111MS001	BG2VE106R1801	Veleka River – Sinemorets village	0.25	4	1.00	0.77
BG2RE92529MS496	BG2RE200R1101	Butamiyata River- estuary	0.81	3	0.67	na
BG2RE00219MS497	BG2RE200R1201	Silistar River - before inflow into Black Sea (estuary)	0.54	2.5	0.50	0.98

Figure 10. Correlation of the pressure index (with electric conductivity substituted by $\text{NH}_4\text{-H}$ concentration) and the nEQR calculated from BI and M-AMBI. + ... outlier

Several obstacles do not allow deciding on either of these two method with sufficient confidence:

- the small number of studied sites of this river type

- the limitation of the BI assessment (lack of type specific scale on which the assessment was carried out)
- the restrictions of AMBI/M-AMBI which was developed for marine benthic indices.

Therefore, without proper correction or adaptation in the calculation, freshwater benthic species cannot be included in the assessment. The above are some of the probable reasons for the discrepancy between the estimates based on BI and the marine index.

As present, we propose to increase the data set on R16 rivers in a separate project with focus on spatial and temporal heterogeneity. The seasonal fluctuations and the spatial extent of salt water intrusion must be clarified before a reliable classification method can be provided.

3.8 Ecological potential

3.8.1 Background

Annex 1 of the Final Report is a general document on ecological potential (thereafter named GD-EP) and describes the principle of ecological potential (EP) classification as defined in the CIS Guidance No 37. Two routes are possible to define the maximum and good ecological potential (MEP, GEP): the reference approach (as already described in CIS Guidance No 4) and the mitigation measures or Prague approach. The first requires information on the BQE to define boundaries for biological metrics at MEP and/or GEP, the latter focusses on possible measures, which influence the hydromorphological and physical-chemical conditions and, hence, the biological communities.

The GD-EP covers the first steps of EP definition:

- Step A. Identification of closest comparable water category
- Step B. Identify mitigation measures
 - Step B1. Identify mitigation measures relevant to each of the hydromorphological alterations and ecologically effective in the physical context of the water body
 - Step B2. Exclude mitigation measures with significant adverse effect on use or wider environment
 - Step B3. Select most ecologically beneficial (combination of) measures taking into account need to ensure best approximation to ecological continuum
- Step C. Derivation of hydromorphological conditions for MEP
- Step D. Derivation of physico-chemical conditions for MEP, taking into account the closest comparable water body type

In this Annex, we evaluate the possibility to use macro-invertebrates for MEP/GEP definition. We will use the outcome of the GD-EP and concentrate on the remaining steps as defined in CIS Guidance No 37:

- Step E. Derivation of BQE conditions for MEP
- Step F. Derivation of BQE conditions for GEP
- Step G. Derivation of supporting quality element conditions for GEP

- Step H. Identification of mitigation measures for GEP

While step G and H can only be roughly covered from a benthological point of view, the main task is to find a way of defining the BQE conditions under MEP (Step E) and GEP (Step F).

3.8.2 River types where the environmental objectives for ES can be met in HMWB

River types R1, R2, R6 and R15

As some river types do not include any HMWB, this chapter will cover only the river types R3–R5 and R7–R14. For R1, R2 and R15, no BQE specific information or class boundaries can be defined to assess the EP. The river Danube R6 is outside the scope of this project.

River types R5 and R7

Most SWB belonging to the river types R5 and R7 do not show a significant impact on structures relevant for invertebrates and seem also not significantly affected by water abstraction. They show dynamics; habitat structures and in-channel diversity seem to be intact and only slightly to moderately altered. Based on screening on Google Earth, the designation of these SWB as heavily modified should be re-evaluated. Considering macroinvertebrates, there is little reason to assume that it should not be possible for this BQE to reach GES. Indeed, several sites sampled in 2020 belonging to these types were in good or even high ecological status. Therefore, we recommend keeping the boundaries and BI classes for EP in these two river types as defined for ES and not set lower environmental objectives, at least for the river sections of larger rivers with dynamics within the channel. *For smaller rivers belonging to R5, lower environmental objectives are justified (see below).*

River type R10

Also the three HMWB belonging to R10 do not seem significantly altered in the structures and habitat characteristics relevant for the BQE benthic invertebrates, even if we consider the channelization and the reduced lateral connectivity. Taking into account mitigation measures as described in chapter 4.7.2 of the GD-EP, good or even high ecological status can be possible for the HMWB of R10. The result of the sampling in 2020 at two R10 sites revealed good status in one case, and moderate status in the other, which could result from enhanced organic or nutrient pollution rather from the physical alterations.

River type R12

The river type R12 includes sections of the rivers Maritsa and Tundsha. Only 1 of 10 SWB is heavily modified (a section of Maritsa between approximately Pazardzhik and Plovdiv). In-channel diversity and riparian structure seem to be largely intact, although the river like many others has lost its inundation area in the larger floodplain. Water abstraction probably does not critically affect the benthic community. Like for the previous types, we recommend keeping the boundaries and BI classes for EP as defined for ES and not set lower environmental objectives.

River type R14

Only 2 of 50 SWB belonging to this type are heavily modified: Alamovska reka (BG3AR400R018; *see below*) and Kalamitsa river (BG3MA100R002). The latter includes a small reservoir, which probably abstracts water and thus affects the downstream river stretch until the Turkish border.

Although no data from these two R14 HMWB are available from the campaign in 2020, the anthropogenic impacts seem severe enough to significantly alter the benthic communities. However, water abstraction is usually not considered as a reason for not reaching GES. Unless it can be proved that providing ecological flow to the Kalamitsa river has a significant adverse effect on the use, GES should be possible in this case. Therefore, we recommend keeping the boundaries and BI classes for EP as defined for ES and not set lower environmental objectives.

3.8.3 River types where lower environmental objectives for EP than for ES are justified

River type R9

Among 12 SWB belonging to the river type R9 (Danube Dobrudzha rivers), only one is considered as heavily modified (BG1DJ900R1011, Suha reka). It includes one larger reservoir in the middle section, which abstracts a significant proportion of discharge within a naturally dry and karstic region. Hence, water flow is often very limited. Even with some improvement when considering the mitigation measures described in the GD-EP, a significant deviation from GES is expected. Lower boundaries are thus justified.

River type R14

As stated above, only 2 of 50 SWB belonging to this type are heavily modified. Alamovska reka (BG3AR400R018) flows from Alamovska reservoir until the town Zlatograd. It is partly channelised for flood protection and may additionally be impacted by water abstraction. Immediately before the confluence with the Varbitsa river, within the town Zlatograd, the Alamovska river flows underground. Even with some improvement when considering the mitigation measures described in the GD-EP, a significant deviation from GES is expected. Lower boundaries are thus justified.

River types, R3, R4, R8, R11, R13

Most of these river flow through agricultural areas and are channelised. Dynamics and habitat diversity are reduced. In the GD-EP, several mitigations measures were identified, which would improve conditions for benthic invertebrates. The results from the campaign 2020 reveal that some of the HMWB sites are in good or even high ecological status, which demonstrates that it is doubtful whether uniform type-specific methods to assess the EP of heavily modified rivers are reasonable. A site-specific evaluation is thus recommended.

3.8.4 Theoretical options to set boundaries for EP in the reference approach

The CIS Guidance No 37 provides an example how to set boundaries for EP for benthic invertebrates (Figure 11). The example could be a river which is heavily modified due to channelisation. The hydro-morphological conditions are significantly altered and results in moderate status (1+2 in Figure 11). As a consequence, the highest possible EQR in the MZB status classification is 0.57 (3). This value is then defined as MEP (4) and the remaining scale is divided into 5 classes. The lower GEP boundary is set at 0.6 of the new scale (5).

Figure 11. Example of setting class boundaries for EP. Source: CIS Guidance No 37.

This theoretical approach has its limit when a method is used, which does not have continuous but discrete values (and EQR) like the Biotic Index. The possible values are 5, 4.5, 4 etc. until 1, hence “jumping” in 0.5 intervals. As shown in chapter 3.6, changes in ecological status classes regularly occur when the BI changes by one step only. This significantly reduces the options to set boundaries. Defining an EP boundary 1 step lower than ES means 1 status class lower, 2 steps lower may correspond to 2 status classes.

Therefore, we recommend a simple and pragmatic approach:

- For types or single HMWB, where achieving GES is possible, the EP as assessed by the BQE benthic invertebrates should be defined in the same way as the ES (*cf* chapter 3.8.2).
- For types or single HMWB, where achieving GES is not possible, the boundaries of the EP classes for the BI shall be defined 1 step lower as for ES. For example
BI = 3.0 is moderate ES → in HMWB this would result in GEP
BI = 3.5 is GES → in HMWB this would result in MEP

A list of all HMWB sampled in 2020 with the proposed classification results for the ecological potential following the reference approach as described above is given in the data Annex in chapter 7.

3.8.5 Mitigation measures or Prague approach

If the **mitigation measures or Prague approach** shall be followed, the measures selected chapter 4 of the DG-EP are used as a starting point. Tab. 23 of the DG-EP lists the most ecologically beneficial mitigation measures in rivers. For benthic invertebrates and in the types discussed in chapter 3.8.3, the following set of mitigation measures is considered as most relevant and necessary to achieve the **maximum ecological potential**:

- Ecological flow
- Riparian habitat enhancement
- Improvement of in-channel diversity
- Increase habitat diversity (depth, width)
- Floodplains / off-channel / lateral connect.
- Channel enhancement
- Vegetation enhancement / rehabilitation
- Reduction negative effects of impoundment
- Rehabilitation of phys-chem alteration
- Intertidal habitat restoration

Under **good ecological potential**, we propose the following set of mitigation measures:

- Ecological flow
- Riparian habitat enhancement (at smaller scale than under MEP)
- Improvement of in-channel diversity (at smaller scale than under MEP)

- Increase habitat diversity (depth, width) (at smaller scale than under MEP)
- Reduction negative effects of impoundment
- Rehabilitation of phys-chem alteration

4 Lakes

4.1 Descriptive analyses of the biological community

As with the running waters, similarity analyses using non-metric multidimensional scaling (nMDS) were carried out to represent the species communities. Further statistical methods were the Anosim test and the Mantel test as well as an indicator species analysis (see above in chapter 3).

The species community groupings were analysed in terms of region (RBD), lake types, freshwater vs transitional waters, natural vs HMWB, and altitude classes. Although the results of the overall Anosim-test (Table 26) revealed significant results, the R-values were generally low. An R value close to 1 suggests dissimilarity between groups while an R value close to 0 suggests an even distribution. Higher R-values were only found in the grouping by lake types and especially among the transitional waters belonging to the national lake types L7 to L10. These oligo- to polyhaline lakes clearly separated from freshwater lakes and reservoirs (Figure 12 & Figure 13). The Black Sea coastal lakes were characterised by the presence of marine species such as *Heterochaeta costata* (Oligochaeta) and *Ecrobia maritima* (Gastropoda). Table 27 shows the species that were found exclusively in these lake types (determined by indicator species analyses).

Table 26. Results of the Anosim statistics with the R-value and the significance values.

Grouping	R	p	Significance
River basin district	0.1389	<0.001	***
Type	0.5069	<0.001	***
Freshwater/Transitional	0.5011	<0.001	***
natural/HMWB	0.1325	<0.05	*
Altitude class	0.0362	0.2347	ns

Figure 12. nMDS plot on macroinvertebrates abundance data in BG lakes, grouped by lake types. Database: sampling campaigns 2020

Figure 13. nMDS plot on macroinvertebrates abundance data grouped by lake types (transitional waters L07 to L10 against others). Database: sampling campaigns 2020.

Table 27. Results of the indicator species analyses of the transitional waters with the specification of the stat-value (higher values mean that the species is more strongly associated with the type) and significance values.

Species	stat	p-value	Significance
<i>Cerastoderma glaucum</i>	0.298	0.0001	***
Ostracoda Gen..sp.	0.286	0.0009	***
<i>Ecrobia maritima</i>	0.284	0.0006	***
<i>Chironomus</i> sp.	0.274	0.0032	**
<i>Echinogammarus</i> sp.	0.273	0.0144	*
Nereidae Gen .sp.	0.27	0.0001	***
<i>Rhithropanopeus harrisii</i>	0.267	0.0154	*
Polychaeta Gen .sp.	0.245	0.0001	***
<i>Corixa</i> .sp.	0.241	0.0268	*
<i>Heterochaeta costata</i>	0.239	0.0139	*
Idoteidae Gen..sp.	0.239	0.0031	**
Amphipoda Gen..sp.	0.235	0.0001	***
<i>Abra segmentum</i>	0.226	0.0008	***
<i>Amphibalanus eburneus</i>	0.226	0.0159	*
<i>Palaemon adspersus</i>	0.215	0.0165	*
<i>Sphaeroma</i> sp.	0.194	0.0141	*
Corophiidae Gen..sp.	0.193	0.0008	***
<i>Psammoryctides albicola</i>	0.19	0.0317	*
<i>Idotea balthica basteri</i>	0.183	0.0149	*
Gammaridae Gen sp.	0.182	0.0264	*
<i>Mytilaster lineatus</i>	0.179	0.0032	**
<i>Gyraulus piscinarum</i>	0.178	0.0138	*
<i>Tanypus</i> sp.	0.169	0.0006	***

No clear difference was visible when the sites were grouped by category of natural SWB, HMWB and AWB (plot not shown here). Another analysis used altitude as grouping criterion (Figure 14). Although the Anosim statistic had a low R-value, high-altitude could be clearly separated from low- to medium-altitude lakes, which in turn showed a significant overlap among each other.

Figure 14. nMDS plot on macroinvertebrates abundance data in BG lakes grouped by altitude class. Database: sampling campaigns 2020

4.2 Relationship between biological indices

Similar to the analysis carried out for rivers, the (normalised) biotic metrics tested were strongly correlated with each other (Figure 15). A Mantel test as carried out to find suitable biological indices for the subsequent evaluation method (pressure – response relationship). The correlation between various biological metrics and the macroinvertebrate community was not highly significant in any of the tested metrics and showed only a low R-value. The best results were shown by the Biotic Index BI, ASPT and HMMI (Table 28).

Figure 15. Correlation analysis of selected biological indices with indication of the Spearman correlation coefficient. Significant correlations are indicated by red stars. For abbreviations see chapter 2.3.

Table 28. Results of the Mantel-test between macroinvertebrate community and biological indices. The Spearman correlation coefficients and the significance values were shown.

Indices	Correlation R	p	Significance
BI	0.124	< 0.01	**
ITC	0.089	<0.1	
BMWP	0.111	< 0.1	
ASPT	0.132	< 0.01	**
Number of families	0.109	< 0.1	*
Shannon-Wiener diversity H'	0.084	<0.05	*
HMMI	0.149	< 0.01	**

In the successful IC exercise on Eastern Continental lakes, where Lake Srebarna (type I5) was included, the HMMI developed in Hungary was applied. It is a multimetric index calculated as arithmetic mean of the metrics *number of families*, *diversity*, and *BMWP* – all of them calculated as type-specific EQR. Hence, it makes little sense to directly use the HMMI for other lakes, even if shows a significant correlation in the Mantel test. Different combinations of BI, BMWP, ASPT, and diversity/richness metrics did not clearly suggest a certain multi-metric index. Therefore, we propose using the same combination of metrics as defined and intercalibrated for Lake Srebarna. However, the HMMI cannot be directly applied to the other lakes, but must be calculated separately. Besides, we propose not calculating the multi-metric index as arithmetic mean of the EQR values but rather as the mean of the normalised metrics and calculate the EQR at the end. Although the other option has

been used in the IC and was accepted by the ECOSTART group, the calculation of an EQR at the final step is more common among European classification methods and easier to calculate.

4.3 Proposal of a multimetric index for Bulgarian lakes (BMMI)

Although the proposed multimetric is very similar to the HMMI, it is calculated in a slightly different way and hence, to avoid confusion, we suggest using a different acronym: BMMI = Bulgarian multimetric index for lakes.

It is composed of the metrics with each weight:

- Shannon-Wiener index of diversity H'
- Number of families
- BMWP

To combine the three metrics, each of them must first be normalised in the same way as described for the pressure index in chapter 3.4.1. The anchor points used are (like for the pressure index) the 10th and the 90th percentile. In the case of the three biological metrics, they were derived from the data from 2020 (Table 29).

Table 29. Anchor points used for the normalisation of the biological metrics.

Metric	lower anchor	upper anchor
Shannon-Wiener index (H')	0.8748	2.4632
Number of families (No.fam)	7	20
BMWP	12.7	73,6

The normalised values are thus calculated as follows:

$$x^* = \frac{LA - x}{LA - UA}$$

x^* = normalized value

x = raw value

LA, UA = lower / upper anchor point

As the percentiles and not the maximum are chosen as anchor points, some values below 10th percentile and above 90th percentile have normalized values which are below 0 or above 1. The majority of the metric data, however, is within the same range.

The BMMI is then calculated as follows:

$$BMMI = H^* + No.fam^* + BMWP^*$$

For EQR and nEQR calculation see below.

4.4 Significant influence factors

4.4.1 Physical-chemical parameters

The analysis showed significant correlation between the general physico-chemical parameters and the Biotic Index. Electric conductivity and Ammonium-N had the highest explanatory power (Table 30).

Table 30. Spearman-correlation between the available physical-chemical parameters (abbreviations see Table 6) and the Biotic Index BI.

Physical-chemical parameter	Spearman correlation	p	significance
EC	-0.297	<0.001	***
NH ₄ -N	-0.390	<0.001	***
NO ₃ -N	0.052	0.650	ns
TP	-0.278	<0.05	*
SRP	-0.353	<0.01	**
BOD ₅	-0.198	0.125	ns

4.4.2 Hydromorphological pressures

The correlation between hydromorphological alterations and the biological response was less clear than between physical-chemical parameters and BI. The alterations of the riparian vegetation and general habitat alterations turned out to be significantly correlated with BI. In addition, the assessment of general physical-chemical impact (on an ordinal scale and not directly derived from chemical analysis on single dates) was also significantly correlated (Table 31).

Table 31. Spearman-correlation between the hydromorphological pressures and the Biotic Index BI. For abbreviations see Table 7.

Physical-chemical parameter	Spearman correlation	p	significance
VegRip	-0.239	<0.05	*
HabAlt	-0.223	<0.05	*
Toxic	-0.095	0.407	ns
WLF	0.042	0.712	ns
Aquacul	-0.142	0.212	ns
Anth_pres_land	-0.121	0.288	ns
Anth_pres_ph_ch	-0.269	<0.05	*
SUM_Press	-0.310	<0.01	**

4.4.3 Corine landcover

The third analysis on CORINE land use did not show any significant correlation with agriculture, which may be due to scale of land use calculation (SWB watershed) and limited correlation with in-lake chemical situation. However, artificial land cover in the near surrounding (CLC1) was significantly correlated (Table 32). The results of the Mantel test which correlates pressures with the outcome of the nMDS is finally shown in Table 33.

Table 32. Spearman-correlation between CORINE land cover and the Biotic Index BI.

Physical-chemical parameter	Spearman correlation	p	significance
CLC 1	-0.231	<0.05	*
CLC AgrIntensive	-0.135	0.234	ns
CLC AgrExtensive	0.012	0.919	ns

Table 33. Results of the Mantel-test between macroinvertebrate community and different pressures. The Spearman-correlation and significance values were shown. For abbreviations see Table 7.

Indices	Correlation R	p	Significance
Physical-chemical parameters			
EC	0.54	<0.001	***
TP	0.19	<0.01	**
Hydromorphological pressures			
VegRip	0.14	<0.001	***
HabAlt	0.17	<0.001	***
Water level fluctuations	0.12	<0.01	**
Anthropogenic pressure – landscape	0.09	<0.01	**
Sum of all pressures	0.14	<0.001	***
CORINE land cover			
CLC1	0.34	<0.001	***
CLC_AgrIntensive	0.12	<0.01	**

Summarising, the analysis revealed a higher variability in the correlations between pressures and biological response in lakes as compared with rivers, However, the outcome is still significant and demonstrates an impact from different pressure groups on the benthic invertebrates in the littoral of lakes.

4.5 Pressure – Response Relationship

4.5.1 Pressure Index calculation

The pressure index included the following parameters from Corine Landcover (CLC1, hydromorphological pressures (Sum of Pressures, with HabAlt and Aquaculture having double weight) and chemical parameters (TP, NH₄-N with double weight). The Pressure Index PI was calculated as the sum of the normalized values of the stressors. The data were normalized within the range of the 10th and the 90th % percentiles. For TP, type-specific anchor points were used as defined in Annex 2 Phytoplankton of the Final Report. While the normalisation of the chemical values was calculated as described above for the rivers, the hydromorphological pressure values (which can reach have between 0 and 3) were divided by 3 to achieve the same range of 0–1.

$$PI = CLC1^* + Sum.of.pressures^* + TP^* + 2 \cdot NH_4^*$$

4.5.2 Relationship between pressure index and BMMI

The linear regression model between pressure index and BMMI is shown in Figure 16 and summarised in Table 34. R^2 is low (0.14) and below the threshold considered as prerequisite in the IC Guidance documents (0.25). The high variability also among lakes with comparable pressure situation is partly due to methodology (only 1 sample also from large lakes) and partly due to type-specific differences.

Figure 16. Correlation between the pressure index PI and the BMMI.

Table 34. Linear regression model Pressure Index PI vs BMMI.

Linear regression model: BMMI ~ Pressure Index PI	
Call: lm(formula = BMMI ~ PI, data = pc1)	
Residuals: Min 1Q Median 3Q Max -0.63311 -0.22182 -0.04904 0.17530 1.25187	
Coefficients: Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(> t) (Intercept) 0.68578 0.06151 11.15 < 2e-16 *** PI -0.06676 0.01918 -3.48 0.000833 ***	
Signif. Codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1	
Residual standard error: 0.3412 on 76 degrees of freedom (1 observation deleted due to missingness)	
Multiple R-squared: 0.1375, Adjusted R-squared: 0.1261	
F-statistic: 12.11 on 1 and 76 DF, p-value: 0.0008327	

Like in the analysis on rivers and in line with the statistical approaches recommended by Böhmer *et al.* (2011), a linear mixed model was applied to combine sites from different types and calculate type-

specific offset. This method assumes comparable (same slope), but shifted (different intercept) regression lines in *single-type* models. The analysis, however, made clear that the sample sizes are too low to give reasonable results. The outcome of this model was thus not directly used but adapted by expert judgment to define plausible type-specific offsets (Table 36). They were used to calculate benchmarked values of the BMMI, thereafter named cbBMMI. The regression plot with PI vs cbBMMI is shown in Figure 17. The linear regression model between PI and cbBMMI is summarised in Table 35 and shows a slightly higher fit with $R^2 = 0.23$ compared to 0.14 in the model with the uncorrected BMMI.

Figure 17. Correlation between the pressure index and the cbBMMI.

Table 35. Linear regression model Pressure Index PI vs cbBMMI.

Linear regression model: continuous-benchmarked BMMI (cbBMMI) ~ Pressure Index PI

Call:

```
lm(formula = cbBMMI ~ PI, data = df2)
```

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-0.61865	-0.18143	0.00559	0.16942	0.88879

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.56484	0.05139	10.99	< 2e-16 ***
PI	-0.07613	0.01603	-4.75	9.38e-06 ***

Signif. Codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.2851 on 76 degrees of freedom

Multiple R-squared: 0.229, Adjusted R-squared: 0.2188

F-statistic: 22.57 on 1 and 76 DF, p-value: 9.381e-06

Table 36. Type-specific offsets defined to calculate the cbBMMI in BG lake types.

Type	Offset	Type	Offset	Type	Offset
L01	-0.3	L08	0	L13	0.1
L02	0.4	L09	0	L14	0.3
L03	0.1	L10	0.1	L15	0
L04	0.3	L11a	0	L16	0.2
L05a	0.2	L11b	0.2	L17	0.3
L06	0.3	L11c	0.2		
L07	0.5	L12	0		

It should be stressed that the step of continuous benchmarking is not necessary in the later application of the method! It just aims at identifying type-specific differences in the correlations and harmonising the regression model to allow defining reference values and class boundaries also for types, where not the whole pressure gradient is available.

4.6 Reference conditions and class boundaries for the ecological status

4.6.1 Reference values

The procedure for defining the ecological status of lakes is the same as for rivers and as described in chapter 3.5. For the BG rivers, the following combination of reference criteria was defined:

- No HMWB
- High or good ecological status as classified used the BQE phytoplankton (*cf* Annex 2 of the Final Report)

Already on this general level – without defining additional specific criteria for single hydro-morphological pressures – the number of candidate reference sites shrinks to six, covering only two lake types. In addition, Lake Shabla was excluded due to an extremely low BMMI value, which did not match the pressure situation. (According to field data, 70% of the lake bottom was covered by *Cladophora*, which significantly affected the benthic community.) The remaining candidate reference sites were Chernoto, Gergiisko, Bezbog, Kremensko and Ezeretsko lake.

The cbBMMI values of the remaining six sites range between 0.50 and 1.32 (median 0.786). Based on this small sample of candidate reference sites, a **reference value** for the **continuous-benchmarked BMMI** at **0.8** was defined by expert judgment. It was used to calculate the type-specific reference values by adding the offsets from Table 36.

4.6.2 Class boundaries

The H/G boundary is usually derived by defining a percentile in the reference sites as the boundary. As the number of reference sites in the case of the BG lakes is low, this approach is not reasonable. Therefore, we recommend using the equal-distance approach not only for the G/M to P/B boundaries (as proposed in the CIS Guidance) but also for the H/G boundary. This results in EQR

values at 0.8, 0.6, 0.4 and 0.2 (hence, identical to the nEQR as calculated in a separate step for rivers). The outcome of this final calculation is summarised in Table 37.

Table 37. Type-specific values for the BMMI in Bulgarian lakes/reservoirs (except L5 lake Srebarna).

Type	Ref	offset	Ref	H/G	G/M	M/P	P/B	Ref	H/G	G/M	M/P	P/B	lowest
	cbBMMI		BMMI					EQR					
L01	0.8	-0.3	0.50	0.40	0.30	0.20	0.10	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	0.00
L02	0.8	0.4	1.20	0.96	0.72	0.48	0.24	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	0.00
L03	0.8	0.1	0.90	0.72	0.54	0.36	0.18	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	0.00
L04	0.8	0.3	1.10	0.88	0.66	0.44	0.22	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	0.00
L05a	0.8	0.2	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	0.00
L06	0.8	0.3	1.10	0.88	0.66	0.44	0.22	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	0.00
L07	0.8	0.5	1.30	1.04	0.78	0.52	0.26	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	0.00
L08	0.8	0.0	0.80	0.64	0.48	0.32	0.16	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	0.00
L09*)	0.8	0.0	0.80	0.64	0.48	0.32	0.16	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	0.00
L10*)	0.8	0.1	0.90	0.72	0.54	0.36	0.18	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	0.00
L11a	0.8	0.0	0.80	0.64	0.48	0.32	0.16	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	0.00
L11b	0.8	0.2	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	0.00
L11c	0.8	0.2	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	0.00
L12	0.8	0.0	0.80	0.64	0.48	0.32	0.16	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	0.00
L13	0.8	0.1	0.90	0.72	0.54	0.36	0.18	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	0.00
L14	0.8	0.3	1.10	0.88	0.66	0.44	0.22	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	0.00
L15	0.8	0.0	0.80	0.64	0.48	0.32	0.16	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	0.00
L16	0.8	0.2	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	0.00
L17	0.8	0.3	1.10	0.88	0.66	0.44	0.22	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20	0.00

*) The values for L9 and L10 were calculated in line with the other types in case the “freshwater method” shall be applied to sites with low salinity. However, the recommended classification method for these polyhaline standing waters is different, as described below in chapter 4.6.3.

The development of status classes for L11–L15 is not relevant for the assessment of the ecological status of these HMWB but they are used (and presented in the data annex) as a basis for the definition of the EP.

A list of all monitoring sites from lakes/reservoirs sampled in 2020 with the proposed classification results is given in the data Annex in chapter 7.

4.6.3 Transitional lakes belonging to type L9–L10

The benthic invertebrates assemblages in lakes belonging to the transitional types L9 and L10 (sometimes also L8) differ significantly from those in freshwater lakes. The use of the “freshwater indices” such as the BMWP is thus questionable.

An interesting alternative was published by Borja *et al.* (2000): The two indices AMBI (AZTI'S Marine biotic index) and M-AMBI (multimetric AMBI) explore the response of soft-bottom communities to man-induced changes in water quality, integrating long-term environmental conditions. Currently AMBI and M-AMBI are used worldwide in multiple applications and officially in many countries. They can be calculated using the AMBI software (<https://ambi.azti.es/>, last access on 17 Aug 2021).

While the AMBI and M-AMBI do not provide type-specific boundaries, the national Ordinance H-4 provides class boundaries, which were adapted to the Black Sea.

The Ordinance H-4 from 2012 listed three metrics

1. M-AMBI method (adapted to the Black Sea conditions)
2. AMBI method (adapted to the Black Sea conditions)
3. Shannon-Wiener diversity index (adapted)

for the classification of the ecological status of the Black Sea based on the macrofauna (BQE benthic invertebrates) and provided different boundaries for water bodies with muddy substrate and for water bodies with sandy and mixed substrate. The classes defined in the ordinance H-4 from 2012 are summarised in Table 38.

Table 38. System for ecological assessment of coastal sea waters according to BQE invertebrate macrofauna for SWB with different substrate types. Source: Ordinance H-4 from 2012.

Metrics	Substrate	High	Good	Moderate	Poor	Bad
H'	muddy	≥3.3	2.5–3.3	1.8–2.5	1.1–1.8	<1.1
	sandy and mixed	≥4.4	3.1–4.4	2.2–3.1	1.3–2.2	<1.3
EQR_{H'}	muddy	≥0.92	0.69–0.92	0.50–0.69	0.31–0.50	<0.31
	sandy and mixed	≥0.89	0.69–0.89	0.49–0.69	0.29–0.49	<0.29
AMBI	all substrates	≤1.2	1.2–3.3	3.3–4.3	4.3–5.5	5.5–7.0
EQR_{AMBI}	all substrates	≥0.83	0.53–0.83	0.39–0.53	0.21–0.39	<0.21

H' = Shannon-Wiener index of diversity, S = taxa richness, AMBI = AZTI'S Marine biotic index.

The amendment 2020 (MoEW 2020) brought some changes as a result of the IC project 2016 (Decision 2018/229/EU 2018; Todorova *et al.* 2015). The M-AMBI (multidimensional normalized marine biotic index of AZTI) is used and includes:

1. Marine Biotic Index of AZTI (AMBI)
2. Shannon Index (H')
3. Species richness (S)

Strictly speaking, the method used is not the original M-AMBI but M-AMBI*_(n). M-AMBI (Muxika *et al.* 2007) is a multimetric index for assessing the ecological quality status of marine and transitional waters. It is based on benthic macroinvertebrates and integrates AMBI, a biotic index based on species sensitivity/tolerance, with diversity and richness, designed in this way to make it compliant with the WFD. It adopts a multivariate (trivariate) approach, integrating the response of three selected metrics, i.e. species richness, the Shannon-Wiener diversity index (Shannon & Weaver 1949) and the biotic index AMBI (Borja *et al.* 2000). A user-friendly free software is provided by the authors

for direct calculation of the index. However, the exact program code is not accessible and the user is precluded from fully understanding and controlling the algorithm.

M-AMBI*_(n) (Sigovini *et al.* 2013) is a simplified modification of the original method M-AMBI. The authors argue that factor analysis in M-AMBI should be discarded, since the index does not benefit from it anyway. Moreover, the user shall be able to fully understand and control the calculation procedures. Instead of using factor analysis, M-AMBI*_(n) combines the metrics as an *arithmetic mean of their normalized values*. By substituting standardisation of metrics with their min–max normalisation, the index is transformed into the simple mean of the three equally weighted normalised metrics, therefore, becoming independent of the number of samples. In the normalization procedure, instead of the maximum and minimum of the dataset, the established reference values of the metrics are used as maximum and the Bad extremum is used as minimum. The use of this approach was supported by the experts in the EC-GIG (Todorova *et al.* 2015) as it proved simple, stable, transparent and open.

Four different boundaries were set depending on substrate type (like the old ordinance from 2012) and on the dominant taxa:

- infralittoral small and medium sands, dominated by *Chamelea gallina*, *Lentidium mediterraneum* and *Macomangulus tenuis*
- infralittoral large and medium sands, dominated by *Upogebia pusilla*
- shell sands and gravels with diverse fauna
- Upper infralittoral medium and small sands dominated by *Donax trunculus*

It is obvious that boundaries from these sub-types cannot be directly applied to the transitional waters, since none of these taxa were present in the samples from the transitional waters from 2020. The values are still valuable for comparison with the data found in the transitional waters.

Table 39. System for ecological assessment of coastal sea waters according to BQE invertebrate macrofauna for SWB with different substrate types and depending on dominant taxa. Source: Ordinance H-4 from 2012 as amended in 2020 (MoEW 2020).

Ecological status	EQR	AMBI	H'	S	M-AMBI* _(n)
Infralittoral small and medium sands, dominated by <i>Chamelea gallina</i> , <i>Lentidium mediterraneum</i> , <i>Macomangulus tenuis</i>					
Reference value	1	0.3	3.4	30	0.87
High	0.90	0.87	3.06	27	0.78
Good	0.68	2.12	2.31	20	0.59
Moderate	0.45	3.44	1.53	14	0.39
Poor	0.23	4.69	0.78	7	0.20
Bad	<0.23	>4.69	<0.78	<7	<0.20
Infralittoral large and medium sands, dominated by <i>Upogebia pusilla</i>					
Reference value	1	2.5	3.4	35	0.96
High	0.90	2.85	3.06	32	0.86
Good	0.68	3.62	2.31	24	0.65
Moderate	0.45	4.43	1.53	16	0.43

Ecological status	EQR	AMBI	H'	S	M-AMBI* _(n)
Poor	0.23	5.20	0.78	8	0.22
Bad	<0.23	>5.20	<0.78	<8	<0.22
Shell sands and gravels with diverse fauna					
Reference value	1	1.9	3.8	42	0.94
High	0.9	2.40	3.42	38	0.85
Good	0.68	3.28	2.58	29	0.64
Moderate	0.45	4.20	1.71	19	0.42
Poor	0.23	5.08	0.87	10	0.22
Bad	<0.23	>5.08	<0.87	<10	<0.22
Upper infralittoral medium and small sands dominated by <i>Donax trunculus</i>					
Reference value	1	0.5	3.1	18	0.91
High	0.9	1.05	2.79	16	0.82
Good	0.68	2.26	2.11	12	0.62
Moderate	0.45	3.53	1.40	8	0.41
Poor	0.23	4.74	0.71	4	0.21
Bad	<0.23	> 4.74	<0.71	<4	<0.21

The following table lists the range of the M-AMBI metrics in the data from 2020.

Table 40. Range of values for species richness S, Shannon diversity H' and AMBI for lakes belonging to lake types L8–L10 / L9–L10 from 2020.

Type	N	S	H'	AMBI
L8–L10	17	4–25	0.13–2.73	not calc. for L8
only L9 & L10	12	4–22	0.13–1.86	0.70–3.86

N = Number of sites

The analysis revealed that the number of sites and the length of the pressure gradient in the available data was too short to derive boundaries for transitional waters with sufficient certainty. By expert judgment, we propose using the following range for the calculation of M-AMBI*_(n) *sensu* Sigovini *et al.* (2013):

for S: Bad = 0 Ref = 30
for H' Bad = 0.0 Ref = 3.0
for AMBI Bad = 6.0 Ref = 0.5

Using these values, the normalised metrics can be calculated using the formula:

$$x^* = \frac{Bad - x}{Bad - Ref}$$

x* = normalized value

x = raw value

Bad/Ref = lower/upper end of gradient

By expert judgment and in accordance with the above-listed values for coastal waters we suggest an M-AMBI*_(n) of 0.9 as reference value. The class boundaries are derived by setting them at equal

distance until EQR = 0. The EQR is calculated by dividing the value from the monitoring site by the reference value. A final normalisation as described in chapter 3.5.1 on page 24 is not necessary, since the boundaries are already at equal distances.

We propose using this method in a test phase during the next RBMP cycle and evaluate them for the next RPBM. One of the reasons why we do not recommend this approach immediately is the difference in the sampling method used for coastal waters (*e.g.*, Van-Veen grab, at least 0.3 m² per sampling station; at least in previous years) as compared with the method applied for freshwater and transitional waters in 2020.

Regarding the application of the M-AMBI on lake types, we suggest using it for saline and brackish waters, which means L9 and L10, but in some cases the assessment of L8 might be reasonable as well. On the other hand, oligohaline or freshwater sites in L9 and L10 sites (*e.g.* Atanovsko lake) should rather be assessed by the freshwater method described above for L8.

Independent of the method used, we strongly recommend increasing the number of samples in transitional waters to better cope with the heterogeneity and gradient with the SWB. We also recommend using several dates (which means: years within the RBMP cycle) for the final classification of a SWB. This strategy of “spatial and temporal averaging” could make the assessment more robust.

4.6.4 Concluding remark

A list of all monitoring sites from lake type L9 and L10 sampled in 2020 with the proposed classification results is given in the data annex in chapter 7.

The final Table 37 on reference values, class boundaries and EQR values as well as the status classes listed in the data annex for all sampling sites gives an impression of well-founded and secure classification results. However, the uncertainty of the outcome should not be underestimated and the significant degree of expert judgment in developing the classification method should be kept in mind. One of this precautional remark is the low number of sites per type, which limits the options for a thorough statistical analysis. Another reason, however, is the fact that in almost all cases only 1 sampling site per lakes was chosen and sampled (in agreement with the ToR and the current national method). The impression in the field and the data analysis showed that this was not sufficient in many cases, mainly due to differences in substrate at different shore sections, spatial variability depending on short inclination and wind exposition, and local effects from the surroundings or tributaries. These natural factors add to “usual” methodological uncertainties and cause a high variability of the calculated biological metrics, which can only partly be explained by pressures or type-specific differences.

Therefore, we strongly recommend adapting the sampling design for lakes by increasing the number of sampling sites per lake. In Austria and Germany, the number of sites per lake depends on the lake size (Figure 18) and varies between 4 or 5 samples in small lakes and up to 10 samples in large lakes (10 km²). A minimum of three samples per lake is considered as minimum to buffer the above-

mentioned disturbance factors. In addition, a protocol should be developed to define how the samples shall be combined to get a common ecological assessment of the whole SWB.

Such an enhanced effort increases the costs of monitoring, but also the confidence in the classification result. The intensified monitoring effort is balanced by a reduction of the risk of misclassification – which can make costly measures necessary.

Figure 18. Number of sampling sites (samples) depending on lake size in four Austrian (AT) and 14 German (DE) Alpine and pre-Alpine lakes (Miler *et al.* 2013; Wolfram & Großschartner 2013).

4.7 Ecological potential

Like for rivers, it shall be evaluated whether defining MEP and GEP based on the BQE in lakes is possible, in other words: whether the reference approach can be proposed for the BQE benthic invertebrates in lakes and reservoirs.

In the previous section, we stressed the uncertainty in the proposed classification methods for lakes, which bears a significant risks of misclassification. A status class derived at one date can be easily different at another date, even if the pressure situation has not changed. The risk of misclassification does not result from the method of developing the classification system, as we followed the CIS Guidance Documents on defining reference conditions and boundary setting, but is inherent in the data variability which partly results from the sampling design.

Therefore, it is neither possible to describe the benthic community under the mitigation measures defined in the GD-EP (→ MEP) nor when considering slight deviations (→ GEP). Concluding, the **reference approach cannot be recommended** for the classification of the EP based on the BQE benthic invertebrates in lakes. Even the pragmatic approach of defining EP as 1 class below ES (*e.g.*, moderate status = GEP), as proposed for rivers, is not justified.

In the **mitigation measures or Prague approach**, GEP is defined by removing measures only leading to slight changes in the biological conditions. Tab. 22 of the GD-EP lists the most ecologically beneficial mitigation measures in lakes. For benthic invertebrates, the following set of mitigation measures is considered as most relevant and necessary to achieve the **maximum ecological potential**:

- Enhancement of shore/shallow habitats (especially in the littoral zone)
- Creation of secondary habitats
- Where possible, management of lake level by reducing the water level fluctuations and by limiting the rate of lowering the water level (to allow large and mobile animals following the water)
- Mitigation of physical-chemical conditions
- Management of lake use / designation of protected areas
- Beneficial use of dredged material

Under **good ecological potential**, we propose the following set of mitigation measures:

- Enhancement of shore/shallow habitats (especially in the littoral zone)
- Creation of secondary habitats (at smaller scale than under MEP)
- Where possible, management of lake level by limiting the rate of lowering the water level
- Mitigation of physical-chemical conditions
- Management of lake use / designation of protected areas

A list of all HMWB sampled in 2020 with the proposed classification results for the ecological potential following the reference approach as described above is given in the data Annex in chapter 7.

5 Conclusion

This Annex summarises the results of comprehensive analyses on the BQE Benthic invertebrates in relation to the pressures eutrophication, organic pollution, hydromorphological alterations and general degradation in Bulgarian lakes/reservoirs and rivers, including the transitional river and lake types. We evaluated the existing class boundaries defined in the national Ordinance H-4 from 2012 as amended in 2020 and gave recommendations for adaptations and changes.

The recommended biological method for the assessment of the **ecological status in rivers** is the Biotic Index, which has already been successfully intercalibrated for some types. We recommend leaving the existing (partly intercalibrated) class boundaries for the BI unchanged in the river types R1, R2, R3, R4, R5, R7, R8, R10, R12, R13 and R14b, but defining stricter boundaries for the river types R9, R11, R14a, R14c and R15.

The recommended biological method for the assessment of the **ecological status in lakes/reservoirs** is a multi-metric index similar to the one which has been successfully in lake Srebarna (type L5). Due

to slight changes in the calculation, but mainly as the class boundaries are type-specifically defined, we use a different acronym (BMMI for Bulgarian multimetric index). Like the HMMI for Srebarna, the BMMI includes the metrics BMWP, No. of families and Shannon-Wiener index of diversity. The latter requires identification of benthic invertebrates at a taxonomic level below family (genus, species) and, hence, makes demands on the expertise of the biologists processing the samples. This can be a drawback in the routine monitoring, if less-trained people are in charge of performing ecological classification. The pro's and con's of using the simple BI (like for rivers) and the BMMI in lakes/reservoirs were discussed. While the advantage of using the BI is the applicability by less-trained people, the result must of course be valid and confident, otherwise the saved costs of training and expertise are easily exceeded by additional costs for i) mitigation measures which erroneously seem necessary when they are defined on wrong classification results, and ii) increased monitoring to check moderate status sites and to get more robust results. We recommend continuing this discussion with representatives of the competent authorities during the review process of the products of this project. One option could be to prepare an "operational taxa list" which is the minimum required to calculate Shannon-Wiener with confidence. It should help to improve the expertise of less-trained biologists. Besides, the Shannon calculation should be evaluated and may be not so critical, since the Shannon-Wiener index of diversity is only one of three metrics in the BMMI calculation (like in the HMMI for Srebarna). Therefore, if not sufficient taxa are identified with certainty, the overall classification will only slightly be biased.

For **transitional waters** (among lakes only for L9 and L10), we recommend using the M-AMBI*_(n) index, which is currently used also in coastal waters at the Black Sea. Reference values and class boundaries were defined based on field data (monitoring 2020) and by expert judgment, taking into account the values defined for coastal SWB in BG. The classification results are less reliable than those for rivers due to the low number of data and the restricted gradient. We recommend using the suggested method during the next cycle and evaluate the outcome in a plausibility check. For R16 both BI and M-AMBI were tested, evaluated and discussed. As present, however, we cannot recommend one of the two metrics with sufficient confidence. We propose to increase the data set on R16 rivers in a separate project with focus on spatial and temporal heterogeneity. The seasonal fluctuations and the spatial extent of salt water intrusion must be clarified before a reliable classification method can be provided.

Different approaches for defining the **ecological potential** in heavily modified river were evaluated on the basis of the General Document of the definition of the Ecological Potential (GD-EP; Annex 1 of the Final Report). For *rivers*, the same class boundaries for the ecological status can be defined as for the ecological potential, since the current hydro-morphological conditions or those expected after implementing mitigation measures (acc. to the GD-EP) will allow an improvement until the good ecological status is achieved. For other types, the moderate status can be accepted as GEP and the good status as MEP. This approach follows the *reference approach* as defined in the CIS Guidance No 37. For *lakes/reservoirs*, the current data base is too weak to allow defining class boundaries for EP. Here, we recommend following the *mitigation measures approach* as defined in the CIS Guidance No 37 and described in the GD-EP. Our work on the definition of MEP and GEP raised doubts whether the designation of some HWMB was justified. Since GES is expected to be achieved in several cases (though based on this BQE only!), we recommend revising the designation and changing the category

natural vs HMWB both in some rivers types (*e.g.*, some large tributaries of the Danube, large rivers in the WABD and EABD) and lake types (*e.g.*, Lake Burgas).

A critical point in the methods for lakes/reservoirs as well as the transitional waters is the low number of samples. We strongly recommend increasing the number of samples in lakes/reservoirs and transitional waters to better cope with the heterogeneity, in the case of the transitional waters also to cope with the gradient with the SWB. We also recommend using several dates in transitional waters (which means: several years within the RBMP cycle) for the final classification of a SWB. This strategy of “spatial and temporal averaging” could make the assessment more robust.

Regardless the described limitations and reservations, the changes of existing methods and the newly developed methods are compliant with the WFD and recommended to be used in the future monitoring in Bulgaria.

6 References

Bates, D., M. Mächler, B. M. Bolker & S. C. Walker, 2015. Fitting linear mixed-effects models using lme4. *Journal of Statistical Software* 67(1):1-48.

Bates, D., M. Maechler & B. Bolker, 2012. Linear mixed-effects models using S4 classes. R Package Version 3.1.3. Available: <http://CRANR-project.org/package=lme4>.

Birk, S., J. Böhmer, F. Schöll, J. Aroviita, K. Arbaciauskas, M. van den Berg, B. Bis, S. Ciadamidaro, G. Chiriac, E. Elexova, W. Gabriels, R. Garbea, R. K. Johnson, P. Leitner, Z. Mihaljević, A. Mikulec, B. Muñoz, P. Navarro, D. Nemejcova, G. Ofenböck, L. Opatrilova, D. Ozolins, P. Panek, N. Rotaru, R. Soufi, A. K. Schartau, I. Stanković, H. Timm, G. Urbanič, G. Varbiro & G. Wolfram, 2016. XGIG Large River Intercalibration Exercise – Milestone 6 Report. Intercalibrating the national classifications of ecological status for very large rivers in Europe, Biological Quality Element: Benthic Invertebrates (Version 1 – August 2016).

Böhmer, J., S. Birk, N. Willby, G. Phillips & S. Poikane, 2011. Approaches for Metric Standardisation in Intercalibration: Reference Benchmarking, Alternative Benchmarking and Continuous Benchmarking in comparison. unpubl. paper, JRC, Ispra.

Borics, G., G. Wolfram, G. Chiriac, D. Belkinova, K. Donabaum & S. Poikane, 2018. Intercalibration of the national classifications of ecological status for Eastern Continental lakes. Biological quality Element: Phytoplankton. EUR 29338 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.

Borja, Á., J. Franco & V. Pérez, 2000. A marine biotic index to establish the ecological quality of soft bottom benthos within European estuarine and coastal environments. *Marine pollution bulletin* 40:1100–1114.

Borja, Á., I. Muxika & J. Franco, 2003. The application of a marine biotic index to different impact sources affecting soft-bottom benthic communities along European coasts. *Marine pollution bulletin* 46:835–845.

Cheshmedjiev, S., R. Soufi, Y. Vidinova, V. Tyufekchieva, I. Yaneva, J. Uzunov & E. Varadinova, 2011. Multi-habitat sampling method for benthic macroinvertebrate communities in different river types in Bulgaria. *Water Research & Management* 1(3):55-58.

Cheshmedzhiev, S. & E. Varadinova, 2013. Chapter 5. Demersal macroinvertebrates. In Belkinova, D., *et al.* (eds) *Biological analysis and ecological status assessment of Bulgarian surface water ecosystems* [in Bulgarian]. University of Plovdiv, Plovdiv, 147-162.

Decision 2018/229/EU, 2018. Commission Decision of 12 February 2018 establishing, pursuant to Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council, the values of the Member State monitoring system classifications as a result of the intercalibration exercise and repealing Commission Decision 2013/480/EU (notified under document C(2018) 696). *Official Journal of the European Union* L47/2 (20.02.2018).

EU Commission, 2003. CIS Guidance document No 10: River and lakes – Typology, reference conditions and classification systems. Produced by Working Group 2.3 – REFCOND, Luxemburg.

EU Commission, 2011. CIS Guidance document No. 14: Guidance on the intercalibration process 2008-2011. WFD-CIS.

Hawkes, H., 1998. Origin and development of the biological monitoring working party score system. *Water Research* 32(3):964–968.

Klemm, D., P. AL & L. Florence, 1990. Macro-invertebrate Field and Laboratory Method for Evaluating the Biology Integrity of Surface Water. United State Environmental Protection Agency 256.

McGarrigle, M. L. & J. Lucey, 2009. Intercalibration of ecological status of rivers in Ireland for the purpose of the Water Framework Directive. *Biology and Environment: Proceedings of the Royal Irish Academy* 109B:237-246 doi:10.3318/BIOE.2009.109.3.237.

Miler, O., M. Brauns, J. Böhmer & M. Pusch, 2013. Feinabstimmung des Bewertungsverfahrens von Seen mittels Makrozoobenthos“ (Projekt-Nr. O 5.10/2011). Studie im Auftrag der Länderarbeitsgemeinschaft Wasser, Berlin.

Mischke, U., G. Wolfram, J. Van Wichelen, D. Hlúbiková, D. Belkinova, L. Opatrilova, K. Piirsoo, I. Stanković, G. Varbiro, G. Borics, J. Jekabsone, J. Stankeviciene, T. Virbickas, J. Picińska-Faltnowicz, P. Panek, N. Rotaru, R. Garbea & M. Placha, 2016. XGIG Large River Intercalibration Exercise – Milestone 6 Report. Intercalibrating the national classifications of ecological status for very large rivers in Europe. *Biological Quality Element: Phytoplankton*, 1. Version – November 2016. Report for the ECOSTAT Group, Berlin.

MoEW, 2020. Ordinance № H-4 of 14.09.2012 for characterization of surface waters. Issued by the Minister of Environment and Water, promulgated, SG, no. 22 of 05.03.2013, in force from March 5, 2013, amended and add., no. 79 of 23.09.2014, in force since 23.09.2014, amended and ext. DV. issue 85 of October 2, 2020. Sofia.

Muxika, I., Á. Borja & J. Bald, 2007. Using historical data, expert judgement and multivariate analysis in assessing reference conditions and benthic ecological status, according to the European Water Framework Directive. *Marine pollution bulletin* 55:16-29.

Oksanen, J., F. G. Blanchet, M. Friendly, R. Kindt, P. Legendre, D. McGlenn, P. R. Minchin, R. B. O'Hara, G. L. Simpson, P. Solymos, M. H. H. Stevens, E. Szoecs & H. Wagner, 2020. Vegan: Community Ecology Package. Package version 2.5–7, <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=vegan>.

Pavluk, T., A. Bij de Vaate & H. A. Leslie, 2000. Development of an Index of Trophic Completeness for benthic macroinvertebrate communities in flowing waters. *Hydrobiologia* 427(1):135-141
doi:10.1023/A:1003911109416.

R Core Team, 2021. R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing. URL: <http://www.R-project.org>, Vienna, Austria.

Shannon, C. E. & W. Weaver, 1949. The mathematical theory of communication. Urbana (Univ. Illinois Press), 117 pp.

Sigovini, M., E. Keppel & D. Tagliapietra, 2013. M-AMBI revisited: looking inside a widely-used benthic index. *Hydrobiologia* 717:41–50.

Todorova, V., V. Abaza, C. Dumitrache, E. Todorov & G. Wolfram, 2015. Black Sea GIG Coastal Waters - BQE Invertebrate Fauna. Ministry of Water Management, DICON - UBA Consortium, Varna.

Varbiro, G., P. Boda, J. Böhmer, G. Chiriac & G. Wolfram, 2016. EC-GIG Natural Lakes Intercalibration Exercise – Milestone 6 Report. Intercalibrating the national classifications of ecological status for Natural Lakes, Benthic invertebrates (Vs. 2).

Willby, N., S. Birk, S. Poikane & W. van de Bund, 2014. Water Framework Directive Intercalibration Manual - Procedure to fit new or updated classification methods to the results of a completed intercalibration. JRC Technical Report, Luxembourg, Ispra.

Wolfram, G. & M. Großschartner, 2013. Untersuchung des Makrozoobenthos im Litoral von vier Alpanseen. Studie i.A. des BMLFUW, Wien, 66 pp.

Wolfram, G., R. Soufi, W. Stockinger, E. Todorov & D. Todorov, 2016a. Report on fitting a new classification method to the results of the completed intercalibration of the EC GIG (R-E2, R-E3). Bulgaria, BQE: Invertebrates. Revised version 1.3 (9 Sep 2016). Ministry of Environment and Water of Bulgaria, Consortium DICON – UBA, Sofia - Vienna.

Wolfram, G., R. Soufi, W. Stockinger, E. Todorov & D. Todorov, 2016b. Report on fitting a new classification method to the results of the completed intercalibration of the Med GIG (R-M2). Bulgaria, BQE: Invertebrates. Revised version 2.4 (9 Sep 2016). Ministry of Environment and Water of Bulgaria, Consortium DICON – UBA, Sofia - Vienna, 32 pp.

7 Data Annex

Classification results of ecological status in rivers

The following table provides classification results based on benthic macroinvertebrates for all **river** monitoring points from 2020. For all sites, the EQR, the normalised EQR, the ecological status (ES), and – for HMWB the ecological potential (EP) is given. R16 will be added later.

SiteCode	SWB	Type	HMWB	Date	EQR	nEQR	ES	EP
BG4ST06564MS403	BG4ST500R1145	R01	nat	20.08.2020	0.90	0.78	G	-
BG4ST06669MS401	BG4ST600R037	R01	nat	21.08.2020	1.00	1.00	H	-
BG4ST06582MS405	BG4ST500R1041	R01	nat	19.08.2020	1.00	1.00	H	-
BG4ST06569MS402	BG4ST500R1045	R01	nat	18.08.2020	1.00	1.00	H	-
BG4ST06569MS401	BG4ST500R1045	R01	nat	20.08.2020	1.00	1.00	H	-
BG4ST65149MS401	BG4ST500R1067	R01	nat	23.08.2020	1.00	1.00	H	-
BG4ST65341MS401	BG4ST500R058	R01	nat	22.08.2020	1.00	1.00	H	-
BG4ST65891MS402	BG4ST500R1041	R01	nat	19.08.2020	1.00	1.00	H	-
BG4ME47389MS403	BG4ME700R096	R01	nat	08.08.2020	1.00	1.00	H	-
BG4ME47521MS401	BG4ME700R094	R03	nat	27.08.2020	1.15	1.00	H	-
BG4ST65141MS750	BG4ST500R068	R03	HMWB	24.08.2020	0.58	0.41	M	GEP
BG3AR00159MS0040	BG3AR100R006	R03	HMWB	15.09.2020	0.69	0.54	M	GEP
BG3AR00951MS0385	BG3AR900R045	R03	nat	14.09.2020	1.15	1.00	H	-
BG3AR00773MS0270	BG3AR700R039	R03	nat	26.08.2020	0.92	0.83	H	-
BG3AR00721MS0221	BG3AR700R038	R03	HMWB	26.08.2020	1.04	1.00	H	MEP
BG3MA00094MS1462	BG3MA900R200	R03	HMWB	12.08.2020	1.04	1.00	H	MEP
BG3MA00094MS1461	BG3MA900R200	R03	HMWB	12.08.2020	0.69	0.54	M	GEP
BG3MA05295MS0630	BG3MA500R115	R03	nat	13.08.2020	0.69	0.54	M	-
BG3TU00723MS0171	BG3TU700R029	R03	HMWB	03.09.2020	0.92	0.83	H	MEP
BG3TU00999MS0380	BG3TU900R060	R03	nat	01.09.2020	1.15	1.00	H	-
BG4ME00478MS170	BG4ME700R092	R03	nat	28.08.2020	0.58	0.41	M	-
BG4ME04569MS401	BG4ME500R108	R03	nat	26.08.2020	0.69	0.54	M	-
BG3MA00523MS0594	BG3MA500R104	R03	nat	13.08.2020	0.92	0.83	H	-
BG3MA00995MS1571	BG3MA900R230	R03	nat	11.08.2020	0.81	0.68	G	-
BG3MA00997MS1580	BG3MA900R230	R03	nat	11.08.2020	1.04	1.00	H	-
BG2KA09153MS208	BG2KA900R1019	R04	HMWB	26.09.2020	0.77	0.63	G	MEP
BG1IS04229MS1290	BG1IS200R1342	R04	HMWB	16.08.2020	0.88	0.76	G	MEP
BG1IS00061MS150	BG1IS600R1016	R04	HMWB	17.08.2020	0.88	0.76	G	MEP
BG2KA900R1020	BG2KA900R1020	R04	HMWB	26.09.2020	0.88	0.76	G	MEP
BG2KA47522MS452	BG2KA578R1003	R04	HMWB	25.09.2020	0.77	0.63	G	MEP
BG4ST00631MS320	BG4ST300R073	R05	HMWB	24.08.2020	0.82	0.70	G	GEP
BG4ST06541MS403	BG4ST500R1052	R05	nat	22.08.2020	0.93	0.86	H	-
BG4ST65333MS403	BG4ST500R057	R05	HMWB	23.08.2020	0.93	0.86	H	MEP
BG3MA05213MS0570	BG3MA500R103	R05	HMWB	21.08.2020	0.70	0.56	M	<GEP
BG3TU00937MS0290	BG3TU900R042	R05	nat	02.09.2020	0.82	0.70	G	-
BG4ME47319MS409	BG4ME700R103	R05	nat	26.08.2020	1.05	1.00	H	-
BG4ME04792MS401	BG4ME700R091	R05	nat	27.08.2020	0.82	0.70	G	-
BG3MA00471MS0490	BG3MA400R214	R05	nat	15.08.2020	0.93	0.86	H	-
BG3MA00861MS1172	BG3MA800R166	R05	nat	01.09.2020	0.93	0.86	H	-
BG3MA00853MS1170	BG3MA800R223	R05	nat	20.08.2020	0.58	0.42	M	-
BG3MA00811MS1070	BG3MA800R225	R05	HMWB	19.08.2020	0.93	0.86	H	MEP
BG3MA04991MS0553	BG3MA400R214	R05	nat	15.08.2020	0.82	0.70	G	-
BG1YN00061MS140	BG1YN600R1134	R07	HMWB	14.08.2020	0.89	0.77	G	GEP
BG1YN00059MS130	BG1YN307R1127	R07	HMWB	14.08.2020	0.89	0.77	G	GEP

SiteCode	SWB	Type	HMWB	Date	EQR	nEQR	ES	EP
BG1VT00011MS010	BG1VT100R009	R07	HMWB	12.08.2020	0.89	0.77	G	GEP
BG1RL09391MS100	BG1RL900R1012	R07	HMWB	16.08.2020	0.33	0.17	B	<GEP
BG1VT00015MS020	BG1VT100R009	R07	HMWB	12.08.2020	0.78	0.64	G	GEP
BG1YN00021MS020	BG1YN200R028	R08	HMWB	15.08.2020	0.62	0.47	M	GEP
BG1OS00611MS040	BG1OS600R1005	R08	HMWB	13.08.2020	0.72	0.58	M	GEP
BG1OG02431MS023	BG1OG400R1219	R08	HMWB	11.08.2020	0.83	0.70	G	MEP
BG1RL00231MS050	BG1RL200R1007	R08	HMWB	15.08.2020	0.72	0.58	M	GEP
BG1WO01621MS1100	BG1WO600R1014	R08	nat	01.11.2020	0.93	0.82	H	-
BG1DJ00096MS1040	BG1DJ109R001	R09	nat	03.06.2020	0.73	0.59	M	-
BG1DJ00043MS020	BG1DJ149R1002	R09	nat	02.06.2020	0.73	0.59	M	-
BG1DJ00042MS040_2	BG1DJ149R1002	R09	nat	03.06.2020	0.73	0.59	M	-
BG1DJ00042MS040_1	BG1DJ149R1002	R09	nat	04.06.2020	0.84	0.71	G	-
BG1DJ09994MS1010	BG1DJ345R1010	R09	nat	02.06.2020	0.84	0.71	G	-
BG1DJ09942MS090	BG1DJ200R013	R09	nat	06.01.2020	0.63	0.48	M	-
BG1DJ00989MS1023	BG1DJ900R1011	R09	HMWB	01.06.2020	0.73	0.59	M	GEP
BG1DJ99499MS070	BG1DJ900R1011	R09	HMWB	01.06.2020	0.84	0.71	G	MEP
BG2KA00195MS002	BG2KA130R1002	R10	nat	23.09.2020	0.93	0.86	H	-
BG2KA00119MS001	BG2KA130R1002	R10	nat	27.09.2020	0.81	0.69	G	-
BG2KA04173MS233	BG2KA130R1002	R10	nat	22.09.2020	0.93	0.86	H	-
BG2KA00513MS006	BG2KA578R1403	R10	HMWB	25.09.2020	0.58	0.41	M	<GEP
BG2KA00043MS301	BG2KA130R1002	R10	nat	23.09.2020	0.81	0.69	G	-
BG2VE08179MS419	BG2VE106R1301	R10	nat	27.09.2020	0.93	0.86	H	-
BG2KA41913MS302	BG2KA130R1102	R10	HMWB	22.09.2020	0.81	0.69	G	GEP
BG2DO00831MS001	BG2DO800R001	R11	nat	04.06.2020	0.70	0.56	M	-
BG2IU00291MS003	BG2IU200R1105	R11	nat	07.06.2020	0.82	0.70	G	-
BG2IU76411MS410	BG2IU600R1213	R11	nat	07.06.2020	0.94	0.87	H	-
BG2SE59639MS355	BG2SE900R1030	R11	nat	01.06.2020	0.35	0.18	B	-
BG2SE400R006RP08	BG2SE400R1006	R11	nat	02.06.2020	0.82	0.70	G	-
BG2SE09613MS015	BG2SE900R036	R11	HMWB	01.06.2020	0.70	0.56	M	GEP
BG2MA00221MS249	BG2MA200R003	R11	HMWB	07.06.2020	0.82	0.70	G	MEP
BG2MA66131MS364	BG2MA600R005	R11	nat	01.06.2020	0.82	0.70	G	-
BG2MA06931MS370	BG2MA900R1020	R11	nat	31.05.2020	0.94	0.87	H	-
BG2MA00713MS004	BG2MA700R006	R11	HMWB	31.05.2020	0.82	0.70	G	MEP
BG2PR00071MS007	BG2PR567R011	R11	HMWB	03.06.2020	0.47	0.28	P	<GEP
BG2PR00061MS020	BG2PR600R1012	R11	HMWB	03.06.2020	0.59	0.42	M	GEP
BG2PR00033MS003	BG2PR345R1207	R11	nat	04.06.2020	0.70	0.56	M	-
BG2PR02517MS278	BG2PR500R006	R11	HMWB	04.06.2020	0.82	0.70	G	MEP
BG2PR00511MS005	BG2PR345R1107	R11	HMWB	03.06.2020	0.47	0.28	P	<GEP
BG2SE00061MS005	BG2SE600R1010	R11	HMWB	02.06.2020	0.82	0.70	G	MEP
BG2RE00219MS255	BG2RE200R1301	R11	nat	07.06.2020	0.94	0.87	H	-
BG3MA00017MS0020	BG3MA100R001	R12	nat	16.09.2020	0.82	0.71	G	-
BG3MA00077MS1060	BG3MA700R143	R12	HMWB	18.08.2020	0.82	0.71	G	GEP
BG3MA00055MS0670	BG3MA500R217	R12	nat	16.08.2020	0.70	0.57	M	-
BG3TU00013MS0010	BG3TU100R002	R12	nat	05.09.2020	1.06	1.00	H	-
BG3TU00539MS0061	BG3TU135R005	R12	nat	04.09.2020	0.82	0.71	G	-
BG3TU00719MS0160	BG3TU570R067	R12	nat	03.09.2020	0.94	0.88	H	-
BG3MA00317MS4229	BG3MA350R212	R12	nat	17.09.2020	0.82	0.71	G	-
BG3MA00371MS0320	BG3MA350R211	R12	nat	21.08.2020	0.82	0.71	G	-
BG3MA00739MS0910	BG3MA700R143	R12	HMWB	18.08.2020	0.70	0.57	M	<GEP
BG3MA00731MS0902	BG3MA700R143	R12	HMWB	17.08.2020	0.82	0.71	G	GEP
BG3MA00719MS0850	BG3MA700R143	R12	HMWB	17.08.2020	0.82	0.71	G	GEP
BG3MA00711MS0848	BG3MA700R143	R12	HMWB	17.08.2020	0.82	0.71	G	GEP
BG3MA01191MS0010	BG3MA100R001	R12	nat	15.09.2020	0.70	0.57	M	-
BG4ST00632MS601	BG4ST300R1174	R13	nat	09.08.2020	1.05	1.00	H	-

SiteCode	SWB	Type	HMWB	Date	EQR	nEQR	ES	EP
BG4ST06961MS380	BG4ST900R1009	R13	HMWB	18.09.2020	0.93	0.87	H	MEP
BG3MA00041MS0400	BG3MA400R076	R13	nat	14.08.2020	0.93	0.87	H	-
BG3TU000665MS0126	BG3TU600R068	R13	HMWB	04.09.2020	0.93	0.87	H	MEP
BG4ME00044MS403	BG4ME400R112	R13	nat	25.08.2020	0.93	0.87	H	-
BG3MA00318MS0232	BG3MA300R043	R13	nat	17.09.2020	0.58	0.42	M	-
BG3MA00229MS0132	BG3MA200R026	R13	nat	02.09.2020	0.58	0.42	M	-
BG3MA00213MS0090	BG3MA200R014	R13	HMWB	16.09.2020	0.23	0.12	B	<GEP
BG3MA00421MS0403	BG3MA400R076	R13	nat	14.08.2020	0.70	0.55	M	-
BG3MA00583MS0698	BG3MA500R129	R13	nat	20.08.2020	0.82	0.70	G	-
BG4ST65334MS401	BG4ST500R061	R14b	nat	05.06.2020	0.64	0.59	M	-
BG4ST65371MS720	BG4ST500R055	R14c	nat	06.06.2020	0.94	0.88	H	-
BG3AR00003MS0003	BG3AR100R001	R14c	nat	02.06.2020	0.94	0.88	H	-
BG3AR00661MS0206	BG3AR600R024	R14c	nat	04.06.2020	1.18	1.00	H	-
BG3AR00161MS0043	BG3AR100R007	R14c	nat	03.06.2020	0.94	0.88	H	-
BG3AR02949MS1059	BG3AR200R009	R14c	nat	03.06.2020	0.94	0.88	H	-
BG3MA0B112MSB002	BG3MA100R220	R14c	nat	02.06.2020	0.94	0.88	H	-
BG3TU00552MS0080	BG3TU500R018	R14a	nat	01.06.2020	0.47	0.28	P	-
BG3TU00741MS0001	BG3TU100R001	R14c	nat	01.06.2020	0.82	0.70	G	-
BG4ST00622MS900	BG4ST200R077	R15	nat	25.08.2020	0.93	0.86	H	-
BG1IS00416MS049	BG1IS100R1124	R15	nat	16.08.2020	0.70	0.55	M	-
BG1OS07112MS100	BG1OS700R1111	R15	nat	13.08.2020	0.93	0.86	H	-
BG2VE08633MS425	BG2VE700R1601	R15	nat	28.09.2020	0.93	0.86	H	-
BG2VE08671MS426	BG2VE700R1601	R15	nat	28.09.2020	0.70	0.55	M	-
BG2PR211MS002	BG2PR210R1005	R15	nat	21.09.2020	0.81	0.69	G	-
BG4ME00481MS140	BG4ME800R084	R15	nat	28.08.2020	0.93	0.86	H	-
BG2IU07211MS404	BG2IU200R1005	R16	nat	31.08.2020	na			-
BG2IU00081MS254	BG2IU800R1115	R16	nat	30.08.2020	na			-
BG2IU200R005RP14	BG2IU200R1005	R16	nat	02.09.2020	na			-
BG2IU6915MS002	BG2IU600R1013	R16	nat	31.08.2020	na			-
BG2SE00219MS228	BG2SE200R1101	R16	nat	04.09.2020	na	see section 3.7.2		-
BG2SE81MS008	BG2SE800R020	R16	HMWB	03.09.2020	na			-
BG2VE111MS001	BG2VE106R1801	R16	nat	29.09.2020	na			-
BG2RE92529MS496	BG2RE200R1101	R16	nat	27.08.2020	na			-
BG2RE00219MS497	BG2RE200R1201	R16	nat	28.08.2020	na			-

Classification results of ecological status in lakes and reservoirs

The following table provides classification results based on benthic macroinvertebrates for all **lake/reservoir** monitoring points from 2020. For all sites, the EQR, the normalised EQR, and the ecological status (ES) is given. The results for the transitional waters L9 and L10 are preliminary and should not be used with caution. No EQR values are given for HMWB, which shall be assessed based on the mitigation measures approach according to the CIS Guidance No 37.

SiteCode	SWB	Type	HMWB	Date	EQR	nEQR	ES
BG4ST65891MS815	BG4ST600L1007	L01	nat	10.08.2020	0.40	0.40	M
BG4ST65349MS825	BG4ST500L1010	L01	nat	11.08.2020	0.68	0.68	G
BG1IS94733MS071	BG1IS900L1002	L01	HMWB	06.08.2020	0.32	0.32	P
BG4ME0000NMS003	BG4ME700L1009	L01	nat	13.08.2020	1.10	1.00	H
BG4ME47382MS815	BG4ME700L1009	L01	nat	14.08.2020	0.97	0.97	H

SiteCode	SWB	Type	HMWB	Date	EQR	nEQR	ES
BG1YN92233MS051	BG1YN900L1014	L02	HMWB	24.07.2020	0.50	0.50	M
BG1YN62953MS041	BG1YN600L1019	L02	HMWB	25.07.2020	0.82	0.82	H
BG1YN06295MS180	BG1YN600L1019	L02	HMWB	25.07.2020	0.84	0.84	H
BG1IS69539MS041	BG1IS600L1014	L02	HMWB	04.08.2020	0.63	0.63	G
BG1IS22919MS031	BG1IS200L1021	L02	HMWB	03.08.2020	0.80	0.80	G
BG3AR00086MS0290	BG3AR800L041	L03	nat	25.07.2020	0.66	0.66	G
BG3MA09549MS1510	BG3MA900L205	L03	HMWB	20.07.2020	0.32	0.32	P
BG3MA06481MS0740	BG3MA600L138	L03	HMWB	08.07.2020	0.72	0.72	G
BG3MA92259MS1410	BG3MA900L192	L03	HMWB	21.07.2020	0.94	0.94	H
BG4ME02661MS915	BG4DO600L119	L03	HMWB	11.07.2020	0.33	0.33	P
BG4ME02661MS914	BG4DO600L119	L03	HMWB	11.07.2020	0.66	0.66	G
BG4ST00691MS805	BG4ST900L1012	L04	HMWB	15.07.2020	1.14	1.00	H
BG1L04NVHM001_EEA	BG1NV200R1001	L04	nat	05.08.2020	0.80	0.80	H
BG1WO03496MS031	BG1WO300L018	L04	HMWB	16.07.2020	0.84	0.84	H
BG2KA47379MS488	BG2KA400L044	L04	AWB	12.07.2020	0.37	0.37	P
BG2IU200L019RP18	BG2IU200L019	L05a	nat	28.07.2020	0.75	0.75	G
BG2IU200L005RP15	BG2IU200R1005	L05a	nat	27.08.2020	0.72	0.72	G
BG3L06MANA003_EEA	BG3MA350R212	L06	nat	05.08.2020	0.83	0.83	H
BG3L06MANA002_EEA	BG3MA350R211	L06	nat	04.08.2020	0.40	0.40	M
BG4L06MENA001_EEA	BG4ME500R107	L06	HMWB	13.07.2020	0.37	0.37	P
BG2DO10000MS483	BG2DO700L018	L07	nat	06.08.2020	1.40	1.00	H
BG2DO10000MS007	BG2DO700L018	L07	nat	05.08.2020	0.29	0.29	P
BG2MA10000MS007	BG2MA107L002	L07	HMWB	15.07.2020	0.89	0.89	H
BG2IU10000MS004	BG2IU200L017	L08	nat	22.07.2020	0.80	0.80	H
BG2IU00061MS258	BG2IU600L018	L08	nat	29.07.2020	0.37	0.37	P
BG2IU20000MS257	BG2IU200L007	L08	nat	21.07.2020	0.58	0.58	M
BG2SE90000MS022	BG2SE900L037	L08	HMWB	13.07.2020	0.72	0.72	G
BG2SE90000MS024	BG2SE900L037	L08	HMWB	14.07.2020	0.50	0.50	M
BG2MA00611MS008	BG2MA100L001	L09	HMWB	16.07.2020	0.56	0.56	M
BG2MA00019MS009	BG2MA100L001	L09	HMWB	17.07.2020	0.65	0.65	G
BG2PR00155MS012	BG2PR100L002	L09	HMWB	14.08.2020	0.50	0.50	M
BG2PR00191MS010	BG2PR100L003	L09	HMWB	14.08.2020	0.61	0.61	G
BG2PR00155MS018	BG2PR900L020	L09	AWB	10.08.2020	0.60	0.60	G
BG2PR00155MS016	BG2PR100L001	L09	HMWB	11.08.2020	0.45	0.45	M
BG2PR00155MS013	BG2PR100L001	L09	HMWB	13.08.2020	0.40	0.40	M
BG2PR01931MS011	BG2PR100L003	L09	HMWB	15.08.2020	0.28	0.28	P
BG2SE90000MS021	BG2SE900L027	L10	HMWB	18.07.2020	0.62	0.62	G
BG2SE90000MS020	BG2SE900L028	L10	HMWB	19.07.2020	0.69	0.69	G
BG2L10SETR003_EEA	BG2SE900L028	L10	HMWB	19.07.2020	0.72	0.72	G
BG2L10SETR004_EEA	BG2SE900L027	L10	HMWB	18.07.2020	0.82	0.82	H
BG2KA47399MS020	BG2KA400L024	L11a	HMWB	11.07.2020	0.70	0.70	G
BG3TU00077MS0220	BG3TU700R032	L11b	HMWB	20.08.2020	0.43	0.43	M
BG3MA00545MS0640	BG3MA500L119	L11b	HMWB	01.08.2020	0.53	0.53	M
BG4ME00292MS905	BG4DO900L117	L11c	HMWB	09.07.2020	0.65	0.65	G
BG1YN04471MS031	BG1YN400L1005	L12	HMWB	22.07.2020	0.77	0.77	G
BG1YN06496MS061	BG1YN600L1024	L12	HMWB	27.07.2020	0.53	0.53	M
BG1VT00891MS051	BG1VT800L1004	L12	HMWB	20.07.2020	0.56	0.56	M
BG1OG00744MS041	BG1OG700L1016	L12	AWB	14.07.2020	0.54	0.54	M
BG1VT00032MS041	BG1VT300L1010	L12	HMWB	19.07.2020	0.80	0.80	H
BG4ST0000NMS001	BG4ST500L1006	L13	HMWB	14.07.2020	0.37	0.37	P
BG4ST06963MS945	BG4ST900L1008	L13	HMWB	16.07.2020	0.56	0.56	M
BG3TU05239MS0040	BG3TU500L013	L13	HMWB	07.09.2020	0.50	0.50	M
BG3MA00631MS0720	BG3MA600L133	L13	HMWB	23.07.2020	0.40	0.40	M
BG3MA04629MS0451	BG3MA400L092	L13	HMWB	02.08.2020	0.89	0.89	H

SiteCode	SWB	Type	HMWB	Date	EQR	nEQR	ES
BG3MA18739MS0071	BG3MA100L012	L13	HMWB	05.09.2020	0.94	0.94	H
BG3MA00324MS1239	BG3MA300L045	L13	HMWB	04.09.2020	0.92	0.92	H
BG3MA00347MS0280	BG3MA300L061	L13	HMWB	03.09.2020	0.46	0.46	M
BG3MA03929MS0371	BG3MA300L074	L13	HMWB	02.09.2020	0.47	0.47	M
BG1YN43199MS021	BG1YN400L1009	L14	HMWB	20.08.2020	0.29	0.29	P
BG1OG00739MS031_L	BG1OG700L1004	L14	HMWB	15.07.2020	1.13	1.00	H
BG1VT00325MS031a ^{*)}	BG1VT300L1012	L14	HMWB	18.07.2020	1.08	1.00	H
BG1VT00325MS031b ^{*)}	BG1VT300L1012	L14	HMWB	18.07.2020	0.03	0.03	B
BG1OG00739MS031_R	BG1OG700L1004	L14	HMWB	04.09.2020	0.33	0.33	P
BG3AR00133MS0020	BG3AR100L004	L15	HMWB	28.08.2020	0.12	0.12	B
BG3MA02191MS0116	BG3MA200L019	L15	AWB	08.09.2020	0.48	0.48	M
BG3MA00225MS0120	BG3MA200L210	L15	HMWB	28.09.2020	-0.07	0.00	B
BG2KA08471MS261	BG2KA800L027	L16	HMWB	26.07.2020	0.65	0.65	G
BG2KA00233MS037	BG2KA200L006	L16	HMWB	10.07.2020	0.50	0.50	M
BG1WO00814MS071	BG1WO800L1020	L16	HMWB	17.07.2020	0.99	0.99	H
BG2SE98935MS263	BG2SE900L032	L16	HMWB	08.07.2020	0.47	0.47	M
BG2SE08331MS028	BG2SE800L018	L16	HMWB	24.09.2020	-0.14	0.00	B
BG3MA00338MS7269	BG3MA300L054	L17	HMWB	10.09.2020	0.23	0.23	P
BG3MA03143MS1226	BG3MA300L041	L17	HMWB	06.08.2020	-0.28	0.00	B
BG3MA03742MS0322	BG3MA300L068	L17	AWB	03.08.2020	0.55	0.55	M

^{*)} 2 sampling sites in 1 lake/reservoir